

AI-PRISM

**D1.33 – Use cases
scenarios and
requirements analysis
(II)**

Project Title	AI-Powered human-centred Robot Interactions for Smart Manufacturing
Project Acronym	AI-PRISM
Grant Agreement No	101058589
Instrument	Research & Innovation Action
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-01
Start Date of Project	October 1, 2022
Duration of Project	36 months

Name of the deliverable	Use cases scenarios and requirements analysis (II)
Number of the deliverable	D1.3
Related WP number and name	WP1 Industrial Scenarios and Requirements Analysis
Related task number and name	T1.3, T1.4
Deliverable dissemination level	PU
Deliverable due date	M12
Deliverable submission date	30.09.2023
Task leader/Main	PROFACTOR

author	
Contributing partners	ALL
Reviewer(s)	WINGS, CRAN

<p>Keywords</p> <p>Human Robot Collaboration; Interfaces to Program Robots; Use Cases; Stake Holder Requirements; Requirements Mapping</p>

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	08.09.2023	First Draft	PROF; ALL
v0.2	18.09.2023	Internal Review	WINGS; CRAN
v0.3	25.09.2023	Second Draft	PROF; ALL
v0.4	28.09.2023	Second Internal Review	WINGS; CRAN
v0.5	30.09.2023	Final Version	PROF; ALL

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the updated use case scenarios and requirement analysis of the AI-PRISM system design. It includes the description of the five different use cases of the AI-PRISM project and the related key performance indicators (KPIs). Furthermore, the deliverable contains the set of hierarchical requirements for subsequent system development: the high-level requirements identified so far by the stakeholders, and the system requirements (related to Hardware, Human Robot Collaboration aspects, the AI Enhancing Tools and the Social Collaboration aspects) resulting from the analysis of the stakeholder requirements. In addition, the requirement analysis also includes a mapping between the pilot requirements and the responsible technical components. This deliverable extends and updates D1.2 with respect to the use case descriptions and the KPIs. The use cases descriptions give a thorough overview of the current situations and the envisioned collaborative scenarios. Details about a Technology Pull / Technology Push methodology that supported the refinement of the use case definitions and the mapping of stakeholder requirements to system requirements is also given. Additionally, the key human factors dealt in each use case are also described in detail.

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
KPI	Key performance indicator
Cobot	Collaborative Robot
HMI	Human Machine Interface/Interaction
PCB	Printed circuit boards
CAD	computer aided design
HRC	Human Robot Collaboration

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the results of Task "Task 1.3 Use cases scenarios and KPIs" and Task "Task 1.4 Requirements Analysis", carried out within the framework of the European Union Horizon Europe Project "AI Powered human-centred Robot Interactions for Smart Manufacturing (AI-PRISM)". This deliverable is the updated version of D1.2 Use cases scenarios and requirements analysis (I) submitted in M6, which presented the preliminary report on the use case scenarios and the requirement analysis. The aim of this deliverable is to provide details about the use cases. Also, this deliverable will provide details about the requirements as derived by the analysis of the industrial scenarios. The requirement analysis and specifications presented herein have been defined on the basis of the stakeholder requirements derived from the use cases break-down towards defining the system specifications, the necessary H/W components and the requirements of the Human Robot Collaboration, AI enhancing tools and the Social collaboration aspects of AI-PRISM. The functional requirements, together with the available technology base and the design constraints serve as the basis for the establishment of the performance requirements that will be interpreted in terms of hardware and software. These components comprise the overall requirement specifications of the AI-PRISM system. A total of five use cases are demonstrated are implemented in AI-PRISM (four dedicated demonstrated related to an application scenario and one generic demonstrator).

First the details about the use case scenarios envisioned in AI-PRISM and the related Key performance indicators KPIs are presented. Details of the use case scenario are presented in two parts. First, the current situation of the use case at the use case provider (**AS-IS**) is described. This is followed by the description of the envisioned scenario (**TO BE**) involving the AI enabled robotic solutions to assist and collaborate with human workers to realize the use case. Details on the key human factors dealt in each use case is described. For all use cases, the unitary objectives and tasks (guided by WP) to propose the relation between KPI and objectives were considered and tabulated accordingly. In addition, the relationship between the use case and AI-PRISM objectives are also illustrated. A methodology to formalize the requirement specifications is chosen and detailed. Finally, for each use case, a mapping between the pilot requirements and the involved technical component developed in AI-PRISM to fulfil the

requirement is given. The responsible partner/s for the said technical component are clearly specified including its envisioned TRL to be achieved by the end of the project.

1. Introduction

1.1. Deliverable Purpose, Scope and Context

The purpose of this document is to provide details about the use cases. Also, this deliverable will provide details about the requirements as derived by the analysis of the industrial scenarios. This document is the updated version of the preliminary report D1.2 Use cases scenarios and requirements analysis (I) submitted in M6.

This document D1.3 (Use cases scenarios and requirements analysis (II)) is a public document (PU) and therefore is intended for the European Commission, the AI-PRISM Project Officer and the members of the AI-PRISM consortium and general public.

1.2. Relationship with other AI-PRISM Deliverables

The final version of the use case descriptions and the requirements (hardware and software) are detailed in this deliverable. This document builds upon the previous deliverable D1.2 Use cases scenarios and requirements analysis (I) submitted in M6, which provided the preliminary report on the use case descriptions, the related KPIs and the requirement analysis. The deliverable D 2.3 (AI-PRISM Reference Framework and specification (II)) describing the AI-PRISM reference architecture, design principles and guidelines to develop the use models has close relation to this deliverable. Additionally, the deliverables in the technical work packages WP3, WP4 and WP6 have a close relation to this deliverable.

2. Use Case Scenarios and KPI specification

This section provides details about the use case scenarios envisioned in AI-PRISM and the related KPIs. A total of five use cases are demonstrated are implemented in AI-PRISM (four dedicated demonstrated related to an application scenario and one generic demonstrator). For each use case, details about the current situation at each use case provider (AS-IS) is described. The process overview of the current situation is given first and the detailed step by step

decomposition of the process is described. The envisioned scenario (TO-BE) involving the AI enhanced robotic solutions to assist/ collaborate with the human worker in realizing the use case is presented. An initial process overview followed by a step-by-step decomposition of individual steps describes the role of the robotic assistant and human operator in the use case. Each use case clearly identifies the updates in relation to D1.2 and clarifies the relationship with AI-PRISM objectives. Finally, the key performance indicators (KPIs) for each use case are detailed with a relevant validation metric and a mapping to the related tasks/WP are also given.

2.1. Use Case 1: Furniture

2.1.1. Scenario Overview

2.1.2. Scenario 1: Painting Process

2.1.2.1 *AS-IS: Process Overview*

The painting process has several steps, consisting of loading, background painting, painting, sanding and final painting. But before carrying out these steps, it is important to correctly select the order in which the pieces will be painted, since the painting time is affected by colour changes and type of pieces to process. Different products also have different number of processes, some need more layers of painting or different and more precise sanding. The step by step process (AS-IS) is shown in Figure 1. The collection of figures from Figure 2- Figure 13 showcase the actual state of each of these steps.

Figure 1. Process steps

Figure 2. Process Control area

Figure 3. Loading area

Figure 4. Staining area cabin (exterior)

Figure 5. Staining area cabin (interior)

Figure 6. Coating area cabin (exterior)

Figure 7. Coating area cabin (interior)

Figure 8. Sanding area cabin (exterior)

Figure 9. Sanding area cabin (interior)

Figure 10. Finishing area cabin (exterior)

Figure 11. Finishing area cabin (interior I)

Figure 12. Finishing area cabin (interior II)

Figure 13. Unloading and Quality Control Area

2.1.2.2 *AS-IS: Step by Step decomposition and requirement derivation*

Painting process:

- **Loading:** The products (either chairs or parts of furniture) are loaded to the power and free conveyor manually. This process is out of the scope of the use case.
- **Transport process:** The transportation of products along the line is already automated.
- **First coat (staining):**
 - **Rotate product.** First, the operator needs to turn the product to reach the face that is going to stain. Currently, this is a manual process, but it can be automated in the use case through an ad-hoc integration with the power and free conveyor system, or through a robot arm rotating the furniture to reach a new face just as the human does.
 - **Apply stain.** The operator uses a spray gun to apply the coating. This process is also manual but can be automated in the use case. We foresee a robot arm installed in each workstation where the human can teach the collaborative robot how to stain a new project and let it continue the batch e.g. confirming the operation on an HMI menu.
- **Sanding process:**

- **Load product.** The product is loaded to the table workstation. This process is currently manual, but it can be automated in the use case.
- **Sand product.** The operator uses a sanding tool to manually sand the product. Automating this process is quite challenging and there are few solutions in industry and none that are suitable to our needs.
- **Second coat (background paint):**
 - Turning chair to achieve all the faces manually done but able to be automatic. This is a process done by a person that can be transferred to a robot with an arm generating this rotating movement needed for the background coat application.
 - Applying background manually done but able to be automatic. This is a process made by a person that can be executed by a robot collaborative in the programming starting process after that just a MENU to be activated by a person to work with this robot.
- **Sanding process:**
 - **Load product.** The product is loaded to the table workstation. This process is currently manual, but it can be automated in the use case.
 - **Sand product.** The operator uses a sanding tool to manually sand the product. Automating this process is quite challenging and there are few solutions in industry and none that are suitable to our needs.
- **Third coat (finishing):**
 - Turning chair to achieve all the faces manually done but able to be automatic. This is a process done by a person that can be transferred to a robot with an arm generating this rotating movement needed for the finishing coat application.
 - Applying finishing manually done but able to be automatic. This is a process made by a person that can be executed by a robot collaborative in the programming starting process after that just a MENU to be activated by a person to work with this robot.
- **Unloading process manually done.**

After a careful review and analysis of the possibilities, the best suited process for a human-robot collaboration is the coating process, by the nature of the actions and the fact that there

can be up to three different coating phases makes this the most promising process for collaboration.

In the coating process a cobot can learn specific patterns of how to use a spray gun in a given product. To do so this pattern must be taught to the cobot by the worker, coating patterns will vary depending on the coating phase, the colour (clearer or darker) and the geometrical shape. This pattern that has been learned can be then saved and used when needed.

All this knowledge can and will be taken into account when generating the planning sequence order of products. Ensuring that the cobot is properly trained for every piece or product that has to be processed.

2.1.2.3 ***TO-BE: Process Overview***

The production process will begin with transforming from a list of pending work orders to a production schedule. In this process, the available information is used to order and organize the parts that are going to be processed in the plant in an optimized way. This plan is generated for the whole week and contains a schedule or sequence of work orders to be processed each day of the week.

First, all the data needed to calculate the weekly schedule will be obtained from the company information services, including the products that should be manufactured or assembled in the near future, and their associated data, like due dates, priority, reference, etc.

Second, the rest of the information needed to create a schedule will be obtained from the enterprise information systems, such as the processing times for all the products in all different operations, the list of operations that each product requires, materials needed, stock availability, and other resources present in the production plant, like the personnel available in the sanding process stage.

With all that available information, the proposed solution will create the weekly production plan. In it, there will be a set of production orders for the whole week, this will include an estimate of starting times and finishing times for each task or operation to be applied to each product.

The list of working orders to be processed is obtained at the beginning of each day. This list comes from the weekly planning and contains a series of work orders to be processed on the production line following the proposed order. The daily working order list contains an ordered list of products to be processed that includes the necessary information for its process, such as the operations that comprise it and product characteristics, such as the type of product and colour that must be applied.

There may be events or states that prevent a manufacturing order from being processed at the time that corresponds to it according to the daily plan, for example, that the robotic painting cell has not been trained following the proposed training plan, that the product to be processed is not in stock due to transport delays or that there are no stocks of upholstery products necessary for the product. When any of these cases occurs, the personnel in charge of the line may cancel a manufacturing order proposed for that day. When cancelling an order, the personnel in charge must justify the reason for cancellation (like any of the examples above). At this time, rescheduling will be executed, which consists of removing the indicated manufacturing order, trying to exchange it with some other manufacturing order that must be processed later in the same week. If this is not possible, the manufacturing order will be removed from the weekly planning and an attempt will be made to introduce another pending order obtained from the ERP. This process is interactive and iterative since several changes to the daily production plan can be proposed on the same day and this will affect both the plan for the current day and the weekly plan also in progress.

Along with the weekly schedule, there will be a proposed calendar with a registry of the coating patterns that must be taught to the cobot. The solution algorithm will generate this calendar when scheduled products in work orders in the current week haven't been trained in the robotized cell. Therefore, cobot must learn this coating process beforehand.

The furniture parts' industrial production relies on human manual labour to perform tasks such as staining, coating and finishing (sub-painting process) or polishing. These types of operations represent repetitive and monotonous movements with light-weight tools (polishing pad) or medium-weight tools (industrial paint spray gun) that can result in excessive accumulation of local muscle fatigue and cause an associated work-related musculoskeletal disorder. The

integration of autonomous collaborative robots in the production cell can reduce the manual painting or polishing process of furniture parts, improving the worker's quality of life.

To create the painting or polishing programs for the robot arm it is necessary to translate manual industrial tasks to robotized solutions, and this requires analysing the tasks performed by operators such as movements, caudal adjustment through spray gun trigger position and polishing capacity through manual force adjustment. The introduction of robotic arms capable of performing complex trajectories that mimic the motion of highly skilled painting or polishing operators is an important factor in integrating fully automated systems in the furniture industry. Current industrial case propose that the robot trajectory will be taught with intuitive programming by demonstration solution. The main benefit of this programming technology is that highly skilled operators can create painting or polishing programs with the complete abstraction of complex programming languages or concepts. Programming by demonstration can teach robots new trajectories or tasks by imitation learning of human movements. In order to automatically generate the new painting or polishing program an interdisciplinary approach must be employed, where several research fields must be considered, such as collaborative multiagent for robotic operative system, ambient digitalization for human-robot collaboration, real-time communications for sensor integration and control and agent level reasoning, acting and control.

The current industrial pilot is focused on the development of symbiotic human-robot collaboration to improve manufacturing performance and improve ergonomics and working conditions, by combining human and robotic systems in complementing competencies. The goal is that operators teach robots how to perform a specific task reducing the workload for operators and mitigating physical distress to perform a given working task. In this scenario, the human and the robot share their different capabilities, competencies, and resources. In this new scenario, the main tasks that the operators will perform quality inspections and quality assurance, as well as teaching the robotic system new programs by demonstration and adjusting the process parameters. A long-range collaboration between humans and robots may improve cell performance rate, operators' thorough assistance and inspection can facilitate proactively support information for robots' tasks execution (adjustment of process parameters). Since highly skilled operators possess the skills and ability of perception,

processing, reasoning, and decision-making, which will be complex to accomplish through a cyber-physical system due to constraints related to technology, computational power, or economic investment. In this manufacturing context, the robot system will have the capacity to improve task execution (sub-painting or polishing process) and the human will collaborate to the robot teaching new programs or improving already existing ones. The power and the repeatability of the robots is efficiently combined with the flexibility of humans, resulting in a reduction of manual labour, and a reduction of time.

One of the main challenges that symbiotic human-robot collaboration must achieve is that humans and machines should be able to improve the performance, the quality and workload while performing a specific task. In this scenario agent level reasoning, acting and control solution must be developed for active collision avoidance to ensure a safe and reliable working environment without fences or physical barriers. In these new scenarios, HRC technologies should comply with safety standards based on ISO-10218-1/2 or ISO 15066. One of the tasks that the current industrial pilot should address is multimodal communication through real-time communications for sensor integration and control AI-PRISM solution, context awareness of human's motion and performing tasks by agent level reasoning, acting and control AI-PRISM solution, and adaptive control for robot programming thanks to AI-based perception solution. As a result of the furniture use case, humans and robots can share the working area simultaneously without physical separation safely, providing beneficial symbiotic collaboration and reducing times, risks, and costs significantly compared with manual operations.

The ambient digitalization for human-robot collaboration is achieved through the integration of scanners or cameras into ROS. These technologies are integrated into the manufacturing cell to avoid collisions and make collaboration possible between robot arm and operators. Usually, two safety control areas are defined, the "slow down zone" where if a human access the robot reduces its working speed by 50% of the manufacturing speed and makes the necessary movements to avoid humans; and the "stop zone" where the robot movement stop if the operator enters this area. Since there are no physical barriers in the collaborative environment the safety functionalities must be directly connected to the ROS and the control system. The LIDAR obtains a distance map of the objects in the scene, so it helps to identify the objects that are near the robot. This allows the robot's speed to be decreased if human is nearby. To

improve human safety, a human recognition system is added. Several Intel Real sense cameras identify and obtain the 3D position of the people on the scene.

2.1.2.4 TO BE: Step by Step decomposition

Figure 14. BPMN describing the painting process in the AW use case.

The painting and polishing of furniture parts in a symbiotic and collaborative robotic cell is performed following the sequence described in Figure 14. The action sequence starts with loading the work order into the system, where the automatic painting software checker verifies if the reference (furniture item) is available in the database. If the reference does not exist, that means that the robot is not capable of performing the painting process, therefore the next step consists of teaching the robot how to perform the operation, using the programming by demonstration methodology and for this, the Oculus Rift Touch is used. The programming can be performed in a test work cell (offline) or in-process (inline). In the To Be scenario, the operator holds the Oculus in his hand and starts by spraying the first item. At the same time,

the position and orientation information from the Oculus is saved, so the robot can use this information later and perform the same movements. Then, in the next programming phase, the operator should verify the performance of the created painting program. Once the program is completed, it is transferred to the robot arm and is tested on a part, if the program does not meet the quality standards the operator can modify some parameters (painting flow rate, pressure, part position, coordinates of automatic rotation table, etc.) if it required or validated the program for production. Once the program is validated, the program is stored on a file system and referenced in a database, allowing it to be later invoked to paint that furniture reference.

Once the painting trajectory program has been validated for production, it can be selected and used in the symbiotic collaborative painting process. The start of the automatic process is triggered by a sensor or operator signal that ensures that the part is ready for the painting process. During the symbiotic collaborative painting process if the operator who is inspecting the quality of the coating (staining, coating or finishing) if access to some safety area to inspect the part in more detail or reprocess the part agent level reasoning, acting and control AI-PRISM solution is triggered to avoid collision between human and robot arm. Also, during the automatic process the operator can modify some process parameters inside in a validated range, this process adjustment is based on the highly skilled knowledge that the operator has in the process and the inspection and reasoning operators' capabilities.

The Real-time Communications Network is a central component in the digital upgrade, helping to streamline industrial processes and improve product quality. The network uses software-defined Networking (SDN) technology to ensure fast and reliable communication between air quality sensors and Ambient Digitalisation modules. This setup aids in efficiently transmitting critical data, reducing latency with the help of optimized edge computing solutions. The paint booths represent a crucial application area for this network. Sensors in these zones provide real-time feedback on vital operational aspects, such as ventilation system functionality and paint applicator conditions, by monitoring suspended particles. This immediate feedback loop allows for the timely identification and resolution of issues such as blockages or pressure anomalies, promoting smooth operation and enhancing the quality of the end products.

The network emphasizes Quality of Service (QoS), ensuring the efficient and prioritized transmission of essential data, which is a bedrock for agile and informed decision-making. Addressing the complexity of the furniture production process, it integrates a diverse array of AI-PRISM components to work cohesively, facilitating optimal interaction and leveraging data derived from various approaches to make more informed decisions. Building upon the SDN core, the network establishes dynamic, reliable, and real-time connections, evolving continuously to meet the changing demands. This infrastructure prioritizes data paths, ensures uninterrupted service based on data criticality, and fosters a centralized operational environment. By doing so, it offers high-level applications and interfaces that simplify component configuration, enhancing the overall productivity and efficiency in furniture manufacturing setups.

2.1.3. Key Human Factors

The coating process AS-IS illustrated key ergonomic factors (prolonged exposure in ergonomically challenging postures) and human factors of increased chances mental fatigue due to repetitive low cognitive engagement requiring work. The key objectives with the AI-PRISM solution will be to increase physical comfort by eliminating operators' exposure to bending while performing tasks as well as allowing the operator to engaging in more cognitively challenging and work schedule organizing tasks. Combination of these two aims provide further upskilling opportunities for the operators. However, the introduction of robotic technology in the TO-BE process needs to consider the mindful definition of changing roles what the operator and the robotic technology is performing, and managing increased cognitive flexibility required to monitor robot performance (quality of completed work) and other tasks operator will be performing. Challenges of developing appropriate levels of trust in the technology will be managed throughout operator engagement activities in WP5. The high-level objectives from the human factors point of view are two-fold: (i) decrease in physical discomfort, and (ii) decrease of mental fatigue/increase of cognitive engagement with the performed process.

2.1.4. Updates with respect to D1.2

From the ambient level point of view, we decided to let the use of cobots out of the sanding process because for technical reasons the use of robots in the sanding process this will be carried out to laboratory level only.

In the other hand, the proposal of scheduling optimization will change actual daily planification to weekly planning adding flexibility to all plant and allowing a more precise control of plant tasks.

2.1.5. Relation to AI-PRISM

AI-PRISM will provide not only an improvement in the quality of work by allowing workers to free themselves from part of the heavy work, but the global optimization of the tasks will allow adding flexibility and reacting to setbacks in all phases of the manufacturing process, removing uncertainty and ensuring a better use of resources. The upskilling opportunities and the development transferable skills will promote workforce sustainability and workforce technology readiness enabling greater job satisfaction and psychological wellbeing.

2.1.6. Specification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Table 1. Indicative list of KPIs

KPI		Description	Validation Metric	Related Task/s, Deliverables	Relation to Objectives
Social	U1_KPI4	Comfort and Satisfaction, with which to measure the perception of reached wellness in workers, since the incorporation of the collaborative robot.	Work-related body-part discomfort scale (Cameron, 1996) triangulated with heart rate and adapted physical exertion scale (Williams, 2017) System Usability Scale (Brooke, 1995) the 68% of the scale indicating above average usability (expected result to be above 80%) Occupational self-efficacy (Rigotti et al., 2008)	T3.2 T5.3 T5.4	O3 O5
		Positive engagement and attitudes toward the new developed process	Technology acceptance model 3 (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008) and Trust in industrial HRC (Charalambous et al., 2016)	T5.4	O5

Economic	U1_KPI1	Quality, measure the decrease in defects or reprocessed parts	20% increase in acceptance of parts. Quality = (Accepted units / Total produced units) * 100	T5.2/ T6.4	O5
	U1_KPI2	Productivity, where we expect to measure the increase in the number of finished units per unit of time, considering available time and cycle time.	30% increase in finished units per unit of time. Productivity= (Total Time used in Staining and/or Sanding Process/Total Time available in Staining and/or Sanding) *100 Cycle Time=Task finished time - Task start time +1	T5.2/T5.4	O5
	U1_KPI3	Capacity, to measure the increase in finished and/or processed units or parts on the line.	+/- 30% increase in finished units on the Painting Line Capacity= Batch size/ (Set-up Time + Run Time*Batch size) Performance=Total number of finished units/Theoretical Max. Robot Cycle	T4.2	O4
	U1_KPI5	Daily Robustness, measure how the scheduling and rescheduling initially proposed relate to the final and real production history each day.	Daily Robustness = N° of products that have been completed once the day has passed / N° of total scheduled products in a daily plan	T4.2	O4
	U1_KPI6	Weekly Robustness, measure how the scheduling and rescheduling initially proposed relate to the final and real production history each week.	Weekly Robustness = N° of products that have been completed once the week has passed / N° of total scheduled products in a weekly plan	T4.2	O4

2.2. Use Case 2: Reduction of environmental pollution with waste from production of semiconductors

2.2.1. Scenario Overview

The key unique chips manufacturing process was invented in VIGO. The process is based on precise positioning and gluing semiconductor to the wire. As the only one in the world IR detectors provider, VIGO is manufacturing detectors with hyper hemisphere immersion lens. The process is done locally by our experienced production technicians using high manual skills, microscopes and dedicated fixtures. Achievable repeatability is less than 0.01mm, even going to around 0.005mm

2.2.2. Scenario Gluing chips to the wire

2.2.2.1 AS-IS: Process Overview

Current process flow is shown below in Figure 15. All steps are done manually by technicians. Chips are provided in transparent boxes from warehouse with full traceability. Each box contains sticker on the top of box with QR code.

Figure 15. Gluing chip to the wire process steps

For each client the chip dimensions can be customized. Possible dimensions are in the range:

- Height: (0.5 - 1.5) mm
- Side length: (1 - 3) mm

Matching components to customer needs makes it difficult to use classic automation solutions. In addition, the cost of experimenting with classic automation for small batches is huge and inefficient.

The most time-consuming steps are:

- microscope focus setup,
- fixture-microscope calibration,
- chip positioning

2.2.2.2 AS-IS: Step by Step decomposition and requirements derivation

- **Loading:**

- Human puts the chip on adjustable table covered by thin layer of wax (wax is used to hold chip) as shown in Figure 16

Figure 16. Chip placement on adjustable XY table

- Human moves table to the microscope nest (see Figure 17).

Figure 17. XY stage placed in microscope bracket

- **Microscope setup:**

- Focus and camera angle orientation adjustment. Angle orientation is useful for later manual positioning

- **Fixture-microscope calibration:**

- Human is quickly rotating screws to move the table to laminate area (issue: non-ergonomic station, little space for hand operation, tiredness related to long time of fast screws rotation by hands), see Figure 18

Figure 18. XY table adjustment

- Human puts calibration tool (needle) in fork shape bracket to mark the laminate and prepare reference point (issue: master tool loose or damage), see Figure 19

Figure 19. Marking tool - calibration process

- Human uses the screws to align reference point with centricity of microscope (issues: many old marks - easy to make mistake during search of current mark, different height of laminate and chip - provides lower precision due to blurry image, time consuming adjustment due to microscope backlash), see Figure 20

Figure 20. Microscope adjustment – centering on the mark

- Human rotates XY mobile stage screws until chip's centre align with camera axis, see Figure 21

Figure 21. XY table movement to chip position

- **Gluing:**
 - Human is dipping the top of wire in a glue (issue: lack of repetitive amount of glue)
 - Placing wire in the fork bracket (forks equipped in magnets to hold the shaft), see Figure 22

- Human push the wire and move the wire down to the glue curing position (issue: unrepeatable components perpendicularity and surfaces parallelism)
- **Unloading:**
 - Human removes XY stage from microscope bracket and waits 20 minutes for glue curing
 - Human removes assembly and returns to the same box with unique traceability QR

Figure 22. Chip glued to wire before machining

2.2.2.3 **TO-BE: Process Overview**

New process should be focused on human aspects to improve quality of work, eliminated non-ergonomic operations, decrease time spent looking on the screen and unload stress related to precise positioning. The desired solution should be based on motorized XY stage, where the allow step is below 0.001mm. Expected positioning resolution is 0.001mm. Wax is going to be replaced by dedicated low adhesive tape or the vacuum suction cup. High resolution camera is needed for pattern recognition. The glue and wires remain unchanged. AI algorithm should be learnt by operator. AI is going to support in vision positioning and motion control. AI should be able to detect surface defects and recognize differences between material like gold, indium,

chrome, etc. Figure 23 depicts the proposed station design envisioned. Human is still in a loop with machine, below steps are not considered to be delegated to the robot:

- glue dispense
- wire placement in the bracket
- wire movement to the final position

Figure 23. Proposed station design

2.2.2.4 TO BE: Step by Step decomposition

Figure 24. TO-BE step by step process decomposition

The Figure 24 shows the decomposition to human and machine in the final stage of product preparation. When the chip positioning is ongoing, human is preparing the wire and dispensing the glue. They work simultaneously.

New product introduction is going to be done using a vision by demonstration module. Human for each new product have to do X pieces manually to learn the system. In the next phase human is providing supervision to AI vision results and do the final acceptance. In case of wrong recognition human correct the position using HMI. When the results of AI recognition and positioning are satisfactory the final phase can be enabled by human.

Photos, positioning and process parameters should be recorded in MES.

2.2.3. Key Human Factors

The process of gluing chips to the wire for the semiconductor assembly highlights the dependency on the operator skills. Although the process steps are easy, the speed at which it can be completed depends on the experience of the operator as illustrated in D5.1 comparing the process completion between novice and experienced operators. This discrepancy in completion time arises due to control of the microscope and effective placement of the chip during the initial stages. Yet, due to the working with small parts and the needs of microscope, the experienced eye strain of the operator during this process is one of the key human factors. Furthermore, as this process can be the bottle neck for the further production, increased time demands and repeatability of the process, the operators might experience higher mental fatigue which can lead to errors. The future process needs to consider that operators independence in the process and that they have certain routines varying from the Standard Operational Instructions to improve their performance (D5.1 operator preparing several stands with chips and other at the same time gluing multiple wires). The high-level objectives from the human factors point of view are two-fold: (i) decrease in physical discomfort, and (ii) decrease of mental fatigue/increase of cognitive engagement with remaining perceived self-efficacy of the operator.

2.2.4. Updates with respect to D1.2

In the previous version, two scenarios were considered. After the consortium meeting and use case dedicated sessions, the final decision was to choose the gluing stick to the chip scenario. The decision was made based on reducing social inconveniences of the manufacturing process, available consortium resources, hardware requirements and possibility of matching universal solutions ready for other partners. Additionally, significant impact for decision was related to limited budget and requirement of high precision.

2.2.5. Relation to AI-PRISM

The most important relation to AI-PRISM project is improvement quality of work and adapting shop floor towards the Industry 5.0. Chosen process is perfect use case for increasing the physical comfort of work and reduction of mental fatigue. High precision production requires

to be long time focused and high manual skills. AI algorithms will support operators in positioning. Frequent high-speed turning of the screws by hand can lead to occupational diseases of the fingers and even disability. Manual adjustable XY stages are going to be replaced by robotic solution, where human is going to collaborate with machine as it was shown at the graph above in section (TO-BE). Vision by demonstrations module is the answer for high mixed volume production where classic automation is ineffective. AI vision will decrease time spent for looking at the screen and reduce possibilities of eye disease.

2.2.6. Specification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Table 2. Indicative list of KPIs

	KPI	Description	Validation Metric	Related Task/s, Deliverables	Relation to Objectives
Social	U2_KPI1	Physical comfort (eye strain, long time in sitting position)	30% reduction of time spent on looking on screen as well as lower scores on Work-related body-part discomfort scale (Cameron, 1996)	WP4, WP5	O3, O4, O5, O6
	U2_KPI2	Mental fatigue - wellness improvement	30% reduction of mental fatigue and mental demand as measured by NASA TLX (Hart & Staveland, 1988) and triangulated with physiological data capture (fNIRS)	WP4, WP5	O3, O4, O5, O6
Economic	U2_KPI3	Cycle time duration	60% reduction, expected cycle time < 2 minutes	WP3, WP4, WP5/T6.4	O3, O4, O5, O6
	U2_KPI4	The robot will successfully glue stick to the chip	Acceptance rate > 95%	WP3, WP4, WP5/T6.4	O3, O4, O5, O6

2.3. Use Case 3: Brewery/Food industry transformation towards Industry 5.0

2.3.1. Scenario Overview

The brewing infrastructure incorporates a filtration system as a vital component among its array of industrial machinery. This filtration mechanism utilizes two distinct chemical compounds, each delivered in powder form, known to be hazardous. The packaged chemicals are systematically introduced into the system with an average frequency of three sacks per minute

2.3.2. Scenario Filtration Powder Preparation

2.3.2.1 *AS-IS: Process Overview*

Periodically, an operator transports pallets laden with powder sacks to the designated location using a forklift. Each sack, with a mass of 22.7 kg, is arranged on a pallet, awaiting transportation to the conveyor system. This operation is primarily managed by an operator, whose responsibilities involve depalletizing the sacks, moving them onto the conveyor belt and ensuring their successful release for further processing. This sequence of actions is performed repetitively. The physical strain associated with this operation is significantly reduced through the utilization of a specialized piece of equipment - a vacuum lifter. This device, readily available within the room, is engineered to facilitate the efficient handling of the heavy sacks, promoting ergonomics and safety. Figure 25 shows the overview of the AS-IS of the filtration powder preparation process. Figure 26 depicts the AS-IS situation of the Diatomite Preparation process.

Figure 25. Simplified Diagram of the Filtration Powder Preparation Process

Figure 26. Diatomite Preparation

2.3.2.2 *AS-IS: Step by Step decomposition and requirements derivation*

The operator's role commences upon receipt of the designated brewing recipe. This document outlines key data such as the quantity and sequence of utilization of both types of filtration powder sacks. Upon identifying the pallets after the forklift has been repositioned to a different location, the operator initiates a repetitive sequence of actions:

1. Reading the recipe to determine which sack of powder is next,
2. Securing the vacuum lifter's suction tool,
3. Aligning it precisely with the next designated sack,
4. Activating it to secure the sack,
5. Manoeuvring the sack over the conveyor system, maintaining an appropriate altitude to ensure smooth transition,
6. Disengaging the vacuum mechanism to release the sack onto the conveyor,

7. Activating the conveyor system for the onward movement of the sack.

Upon the completion of the recipe, the operator ceases the process, signifying the successful execution.

The following illustration in Figure 27 provides a comprehensive visual representation of these steps, depicted through a detailed diagram.

Figure 27. AS-IS Step by Step decomposition

A paramount consideration in this operation pertains to the hazardous nature of the filtration powders. As previously noted, inadvertent inhalation can precipitate significant health consequences.

Moreover, the shared spatial utilization of the brewing facility poses potential risks to other personnel who might traverse in the vicinity of this system.

Finally, despite the ergonomic advantage conferred by the vacuum lifter, the operator's role is not devoid of physical exertion.

In light of these considerations, it becomes clear that the integration of a collaborative robot would be a beneficial enhancement. The introduction of such advanced automation would not only improve the working conditions by mitigating physical strain and potential health hazards, but also transition the human operator's role towards supervisory tasks.

2.3.2.3 *TO-BE: Process Overview*

The integration of a collaborative robot into the operational area creates a bifurcation of responsibilities, leading to the simultaneous execution of two distinct sets of tasks. The human operator assumes an enhanced role centred around system oversight. This role includes monitoring the operational environment and intervening when unpredictable situations arise. Conversely, the cobot undertakes the responsibility of sack transportation. This involves interpreting the recipe data, engaging the now integrated vacuum lifter suction tool, and ensuring the smooth transit of the sacks onto the conveyor system. The incorporation of the cobot thus signifies an upgrade in the process, boosting both safety and efficiency. Figure 28 shows the TO-BE Simplified Diagram of the Updated Filtration Powder Preparation Process.

Figure 28. TO-BE Simplified Diagram of the Updated Filtration Powder Preparation Process

2.3.2.4 *TO-BE: Step by Step decomposition*

The division of responsibilities following the integration of the collaborative robot leads to two distinct operation sequences. Figure 29 shows the TO-BE step by step decomposition of the Filtration Powder Preparation Process For the human operator, the primary duties now involve:

1. Analysing the recipe,
2. Examining the pallets laden with powder sacks,

3. Overseeing the automated system, and
4. Implementing intervention procedures when required.

In parallel, the cobot is tasked with the following sequence of operations:

1. Processing the recipe data,
2. Gathering data pertaining to the nearby pallets,
3. Employing machine vision algorithms to pinpoint the subsequent sack,
4. Aligning the integrated vacuum lifter suction tool with the identified sack,
5. Engaging the suction tool to secure the sack,
6. Transporting the sack over the conveyor, maintaining a smooth and steady motion,
7. Releasing the sack onto the conveyor system, and
8. Returning to a neutral or 'home' position, prepping for the subsequent operational cycle.

This bifurcated workflow leverages the benefits of automation and human oversight, enhancing both safety and productivity within the process.

As before, the procedure starts after the forklift has been repositioned.

The following picture represents the procedures through a detailed diagram.

Figure 29. Step by Step Diagram of the TO-BE Process

2.3.3. Scenario Sorting Return Bottles from the Market

To promote sustainability within the brewing process, strategies are employed to minimize waste, economic expenditure, and energy consumption. A significant initiative in this regard involves the recycling of beer bottles, where containers are returned from consumers to the brewery for reuse. Specifically, Athenian Brewery has implemented specialized facilities for this purpose, processing a variety of plastic crates, each containing an assortment of bottle types, to efficiently sort and reintegrate these resources into the production cycle.

2.3.3.1 AS-IS: Process Overview

To achieve this objective, a large automation system is implemented. Pallets loaded with a variety of crates are introduced into it, where a robotic manipulator is tasked with depalletizing the crates. Once depalletized, the crates are directed onto a conveyor, which transports them to the next robotic station.

Here, another robotic system extracts the bottles, effectively emptying the crates. The bottles are subsequently placed onto a second conveyor for onward movement within the system. At this juncture, a team of trained personnel is deployed to categorize the incoming bottles based on their type, promoting organized grouping.

Post this categorization process, the bottles are conveyed further into the system. Advanced automation equipment is then utilized to accurately reinsert the bottles into their corresponding crates. Figure 30 shows the AS-IS Simplified overview of the Sorting process.

Figure 30. AS-IS Simplified overview of the Sorting process

2.3.3.2 AS-IS: Step by Step decomposition and requirements derivation

The operational workflow of the workers can be encapsulated in the following sequence of actions:

1. A heterogeneous assortment of bottles is transported to the sorting station via the conveyor system,
2. Workers determine visually the type of each bottle,
3. Through manual dexterity, they proceed to aggregate similar bottle types together,
4. They then release the categorized bottles for subsequent stages of processing.

This sequence underscores the significance of human judgement and manual manipulation in the effective management of this resource recycling process within the brewing industry.

The following picture (see Figure 31) provides a representation of these steps through a step-by-step diagram.

Figure 31. AS-IS step by step decomposition

The nature of this operation presents certain challenges that substantiate the integration of a collaborative robot into the process. Given the delicate and potentially hazardous conditions associated with handling glass bottles, particularly those containing residual liquid, health and safety considerations become paramount. Additionally, given the high volume of bottles managed by the line, a more measured operational pace is desirable for human workers. Coupled with an increasingly sparse workforce, these factors underscore the impetus for augmenting human capabilities with robotic assistance.

2.3.3.3 TO-BE: Process Overview

The integration of a collaborative robot, ushers in subtle yet significant modifications to the operational process, all of which are geared towards easing the workload of the human workers. The robot is positioned adjacent to the workers, sharing the same workspace, and operating with them. Its primary objective is to participate in the bottle sorting process,

effectively alleviating a portion of the workers' burden. To facilitate accurate sorting, the robot is equipped with a machine vision system in the form of a camera. This device assists the robot in distinguishing between different types of bottles, thus streamlining the process. Figure 32 shows the TO-BE Simplified overview of the Sorting Process.

Figure 32. TO-BE Simplified overview of the Sorting Process

2.3.3.4 **TO-BE: Step by Step decomposition**

Incorporating the collaborative robot into the operational workflow does not disrupt the established procedures for the human workers. Instead, it introduces a set of parallel tasks that the robot autonomously executes. Specifically, these additional steps encompass:

1. Utilizing the integrated machine vision system, the robot identifies and categorizes each incoming bottle, and
2. Based on this categorization, the robot sorts the bottles accordingly.

This streamlined process enhances the overall sorting operation within the brewery, maximizing efficiency while reducing manual labour. Figure 33 depicts the TO-BE step by step decomposition of the Sorting Process.

Figure 33. TO-BE Step by Step decomposition

2.3.4. Scenario Packaging and Palletizing Custom Orders

Another critical component of the brewing industry operations involves the customization of client orders. This process, which includes packaging and palletizing, occurs within a dedicated section of the production facility. Client orders demonstrate a dynamic character, signifying that each order is unique, consisting of varying quantities and types of beer products. Despite this variability, all items are consolidated onto a single pallet.

2.3.4.1 AS-IS: Process Overview

Situated within the designated area are several pallets, each one laden with a specific product type, which could range from crates of beer bottles and cans to substantial beer kegs. These product-filled pallets are strategically positioned around unladen pallets, forming an orthogonal configuration.

The worker's responsibility involves studying the customer's invoice, identifying the requested products via their Stock Keeping Units (SKUs), and subsequently transporting them from their respective pallets to an empty one. This procedure can be visualized as a star-like pattern of movement.

Upon completion of the pallet loading process, a forklift is signalled to collect the prepared pallet and transport it to the truck loading area. Figure 34 shows the AS-IS Simplified overview of the Packaging and Palletizing Process.

Figure 34. AS-IS Simplified overview of the Packaging and Palletizing Process

2.3.4.2 AS-IS: Step by Step decomposition and requirements derivation

The roles and responsibilities of the worker within this process can be enumerated as follows:

1. Analysing the details within the customer's invoice,
2. Identifying an available, unladen pallet to be utilized,
3. Reading the specific item entry from the invoice,
4. Locating the corresponding product pallet,
5. Navigating towards the identified product pallet,
6. Manually securing the specified product,
7. Transporting the product to the designated empty pallet,
8. Placing the product onto the pallet,
9. Replicating steps 3-8 as required until all items on the invoice are processed,
10. Signalling the forklift operator once the pallet has been fully loaded and is ready for transport.

The Figure 35 shows the AS-IS step by step decomposition of Packaging and Palletizing Process.

Figure 35. AS-IS Step by Step decomposition

Given the physical nature of this operational process, there's a tangible risk of the worker developing musculoskeletal disorders due to the repetitive and strenuous actions involved. Hence, the integration of a collaborative robot into the procedure would be beneficial. By automating some of these labour-intensive tasks, a robot could significantly alleviate the physical strain on workers, thereby enhancing their wellbeing and productivity within the brewing industry.

2.3.4.3 TO-BE: Process Overview

By incorporating an Autonomous Mobile Robot (AMR) into the operational flow, the burden of manual heavy lifting on the worker is significantly mitigated. Instead of directly transporting products to the pallet, the worker can now place them onto the AMR, which is programmed to closely trail the worker. This adjustment allows for multiple products to be moved in a single operation, thereby diminishing the degree of physical exertion and reducing the time spent on this task. The movement pattern also transitions from a star-like shape to a more streamlined

circular pattern, further optimizing the workflow in this aspect of the brewing industry. Figure 36 shows the TO-BE Simplified overview of the Packaging & Palletizing Process.

Figure 36. TO-BE Simplified overview of the Packaging and Palletizing Process

2.3.4.4 TO-BE: Step by Step decomposition

With the integration of the Autonomous Mobile Robot (AMR) into the workflow, the operational steps are updated as follows:

1. Examining the customer's invoice,
2. Determining the unladen pallet to be used,
3. Activating the AMR's 'Follow-Me' mode,
4. Reviewing the specific item on the list,
5. Identifying the corresponding product pallet,
6. Proceeding towards the located product pallet,
7. Securing the product,
8. Placing the product onto the AMR,
9. Repeating steps 4-8 until the AMR's capacity is reached,
10. Navigating to the designated empty pallet,
11. Retrieving the product from the AMR,
12. Depositing it onto the designated pallet,
13. Continuing steps 11-12 until the AMR is emptied,
14. Iterating through the entire process until all items from the list have been processed,
15. Alerting the forklift operator once the fully loaded pallet is ready for transport.

This updated sequence ensures an efficient and ergonomically optimized workflow, enhancing the overall productivity and worker's wellbeing within the brewing industry. The TO-BE step by step decomposition of the Packaging & Palletizing Process is showed in Figure 37.

Figure 37. TO-BE Step by Step decomposition of the Packaging and Palletizing Process

2.3.5. Key Human Factors

The Athenian Brewery proposed three processes for the AI-PRISM project and the common human factor in all three issues is the physical discomfort. Filtration powder preparation, bottle sorting, and packaging and palletizing illustrate the heavy loads operators need to move in

order to complete these tasks. Furthermore, in the filtration powder process, the operators are aware of potentially unhealthy substances they could breathe while working in that station. Although they are wearing Personal Protective Equipment, the realization of harmful effects increases mental workload. Similarly, during the observed bottle sorting process, the operators need to handle bottles which due to inside/outside temperature differences might shatter and sometimes have residuals of water inside of them. Although Personal Protective Equipment is also required to be used, the mental pressures of working on this high paced process is exacerbated. The high-level objectives from the human factors point of view are three-fold: (i) decrease in physical discomfort and physical exertion, (ii) increase in job satisfaction and organizational commitment, and (iii) increase psychological comfort in terms of technology acceptance and safety perception.

2.3.6. Updates with respect to D1.2

Three out of the five potential scenarios were prioritized for execution. This decision was influenced by a multifactorial consideration, including the human-centric impact, the potential for significant operational improvement, and budget constraints. The workflow for each of these three scenarios was meticulously examined and essential steps were delineated. Upon the incorporation of collaborative robots, substantial modifications were introduced into the processes. These changes were primarily implemented to benefit operators and workers, albeit the extent of impact varied across different scenarios.

2.3.7. Relation to AI-PRISM

The primary scenario involving the preparation of filtration powder implicates strenuous, repetitive, and monotonous tasks, making workers susceptible to repetitive strain injuries (RSI) and other musculoskeletal disorders. Furthermore, the inherently hazardous and carcinogenic nature of the filtration powder compounds the health risks associated with this process. Hence, automating this procedure with robotic assistance could significantly mitigate these risks.

Subsequent scenarios, including the sorting of returned bottles from the market and packaging and palletizing custom orders, encompass tasks that present considerable challenges for

automation. These tasks require dynamic repurposing and rapid reconfiguration actions, making them ideal candidates for human-robot collaboration.

In all these situations, robots need to be equipped with advanced sensor systems to interact safely with their surroundings, safeguarding human co-workers. Seamless integration of the robots with the existing factory systems is also essential to enable dynamic execution of custom logistics tasks and rapidly changing orders. This integration would enhance productivity while ensuring worker safety and reducing health risks in these complex industrial environments.

2.3.8. Specification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The user expectations pertaining to the use case are intrinsically tied to its functional performance. It is often more tangible to observe this correlation in a completed job phase as opposed to the design or inception phase. In every scenario, individual objectives and tasks (steered by the Work Package) have been proposed in alignment with specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). This approach ensures a measurable connection between the predefined objectives and their corresponding performance metrics.

Table 3. Indicative list of KPIs

KPI	Description	Validation Metric	Related Task/s, Deliverables	Relation to Objectives
Social	U3_KPI1 Improvement of workers safety and wellbeing	Reduction by 30% in number of workers working in heavy tasks and high-risk areas (Baseline 20-30 persons) 1. Increase physical comfort by 30% as measured by Work-related body-part discomfort scale (Cameron, 1996), adapted Borg physical exertion scale (Williams, 2007) and triangulated with the heart rate variability data 2. Increase of satisfaction and organization commitment with Organizational commitment and motivational scale (Cook & Wall, 1980) 3. System Usability Score (Brooke, 1995) above 80% and TAM scores regarding perceived safety and	T3.1 T5.3 T5.4	O3 O5

			satisfaction indicating acceptance of the new technology.		
Economic	U3_KPI2	Reduction of operational expenditures	Reduction by 50% in OPEX for custom/dynamic tasks (Baseline 300K-350K Euros per year)	T3.1 WP4	O3 O4
	U3_KPI3	Increase of cost-efficiency	Reduction by 30% in time to execute custom/dynamic tasks (Baseline cleaning 24 hours/day, sorting 12 hours/day)	T3.1 WP4	O3 O4

2.4. Use Case 4: Adaptable & Collaborative Workstation

2.4.1. Scenario Overview

2.4.2. Scenario 1: Packaging & Quality Control of Hoods

2.4.2.1 AS-IS: Process Overview

At the end of the assembly line, we have a Quality Control Check Box where we are doing some operation, such as visual check, grounding test, functional tests, cleaning, bagging, labelling and so on, before to put it in the package. Figure 38 shows the (AS-IS) Actual Flow for Final Quality Control of the Range Hood. An example of the current AS-IS scenario involving human workers is given in Figure 39.

Figure 38. AS-IS Actual Flow for Packaging & Quality Control of Hoods

Figure 39. Human workers in action in the AS-IS scenario

2.4.2.2 AS-IS: Step by Step decomposition and requirements derivation

1. Visual Control Process – Visual control on both internal and external surfaces of the assembled product follow Quality Control Specification Instructions made by human operator on the conveyor.
2. Grounding Test – Operator takes the product on the conveyor and puts it on the work table. He/she plugs-in the product and makes Grounding Test with our SPS device connection.
3. Functional Tests – Operator puts the electrical engine in function and checks the engine functionalities for each level of the engine steps. After that he/she closes the hydraulic piston to close the chimney and checks the propeller cracks by SPS device connection and puts it on the conveyor.
4. Cable Packing – Operator packs the cable manually.
5. Sticking of the Packed Cable – Operator sticks the packed cable on the product.

6. Sticking the Metal Label inside the product – Operator opens the glass cover and sticks the Metal Label inside the product.
7. Filter Assembling – Operator fixes the filter in its position on the product and closes the cover.
8. Bagging the Product – Operator takes the product, cleans it and puts it in the sack.
9. Putting Barcode Label and Documents near the product – Operator prepares the Product Label and the documents. After that he/she puts them with the product before the packaging operation.

2.4.2.3 TO-BE: Process Overview

At the end of the assembly line, we have a Quality Control Check Box where we are doing some operation, such as visual check, grounding test, functional tests, cleaning, bagging, labelling and so on, before to put it in the package. Figure 40 depicts the step by step decomposition of the quality control of the Range hood scenario. The envisioned human robot collaborative setup of the TO-BE scenario of Packaging & Quality Control of Hoods is shown in Figure 41, Figure 42 (top view)

Figure 40. TO-BE step by step decomposition of the Packaging & Quality Control of Hoods

2.4.2.4 *TO-BE: Step by Step decomposition*

1. **The hood comes to the work station on the conveyor with the cover open position.**
Conveyor speed 2 m/min
2. **Fixing the product on the Fixture.** Human (H1) operator takes the hood from the conveyor, fixes it into the fixture on the work station, plugs in and gives the "READY" signal to the robot
3. **Visual check illumination and defect around the buttons on the glass surface.**
Camera, integrated with Robot (R1), makes visual check on the lighting functionalities and also around the buttons taking the photo, gives OK/Not OK with respect to the SILVERLINE's acceptable criteria
4. **Visual check on the outside surface of the product.** Camera, integrated with Robot (R1), makes visual check on the outside surface of the product, gives OK/Not OK with respect to the SILVERLINE's acceptable criteria, also checks alignment between glass cover and hood body, gives "FINISHED" signal when it will complete the visual check
5. **Open the glass cover.** Operator (H1) opens the glass cover and gives "OK" to the robot for the inside checking of the product.
6. **Visual check on the inside surface of the product.** Camera, integrated with Robot (R1), makes visual check on the inside surface of the product, gives OK/Not OK with respect to the SILVERLINE's acceptable criteria, gives "FINISHED" signal when it finishes the visual check
7. **Barcode label control + putting the label inside of the product.** Operator checks barcode label and puts the label inside of the product.
8. **Carrying the product from the first fixture to the second one and fixing.** Operator (H1) puts the product in the opened position into the second fixture on the second work station in front of the second Robot (R2) for the Functional Tests, plugs it in and gives a "READY" signal to the Robot (R2).
9. **Grounding test.** The connection of SPS device by the robot starts the grounding tests - this operation completes the following:
 - Grounding test (GND)
 - Isolation test (IR)

-High Tension test (KvAC)

SPS Device cannot continue checking if one of these tests goes Not OK.

10. **Close the glass cover.** After Grounding test, operator (H1) closes the glass cover for the Functional tests.
11. **1 Step.** The microphone takes the frequency of the electrical engine and at the same time, Robot (R2) checks the acceptable values from the SPS device.
12. **2 Step.** The microphone takes the frequency of the electrical engine and at the same time, Robot (R2) checks the acceptable values from the SPS device.
13. **3 Step.** The microphone takes the frequency of the electrical engine and at the same time, Robot (R2) checks the acceptable values from the SPS device.
14. **Propeller cracks checking.** Robot (R2), before starting the test, gives a signal to the hydrolic piston to close the chimney. The microphone takes the frequency of the electrical engine and at the same time, Robot (R2) checks the acceptable values from the SPS device.
15. **Cable packing/Sticking of the packed cable.** Operator (H1) unplugs the product, packs the cable and sticks the packed cable on the product.
16. **Putting the product on the conveyor.** Operator (H1) takes the product from the fixture and puts it on the conveyor.
17. **Movement on the conveyor.** The product moves on the conveyor towards the second operator.
18. **Taking the filter/Metal label.** Operator (H2) prepares the filter and the Metal label
19. **Open the glass cover - sticking the metal label.** Operator (H2) opens the glass cover and sticks the metal label.
20. **Filter assembling.** Operator (H2) fixes the filter inside of the product.
21. **Cleaning of the product.** Operator (H2) cleans the product.
22. **Bagging of the product.** Operator (H2) puts the product into the bag.
23. **Putting barkode label and documents near the product.** Operator (H2) puts barkode label and documents near the product on the conveyor.

Figure 41. TO-BE envisioned setup of the collaborative setting

Figure 42. TO-BE (top view) envisioned setup of the collaborative process

- For Quality Control Check with the camera; here, the AI-PRISM system has to individuate the defects on the product and respecting Acceptable Criteria, decide if that defect is OK or Not OK. The success of this test will depend on the camera efficiency, illumination of the environment (and/or the product surface), the position of the product on the pallet. Sometimes, it should be necessary for the human-robot interaction to get the final decision.
- For Engine Working Level Functionality and Propeller Cracks Checking with microphone; communicating with SPS device and considering Acceptable Values of every steps, the

AI-PRISM system has to give OK / Not OK the functionalities of the product. Sometimes, it should be necessary the human-robot interaction to get the final decision.

2.4.3. Key Human Factors

The packing and quality control of hoods process AS-IS illustrated the potential for the increased physical fatigue and low mental stimulation for the operator. The key objectives with the AI-PRISM solution as outlined in D5.1 would be eliminating overlapping steps operators perform and introduce human robot collaboration enabling not only to increase physical safety aspect (grounding testing performed by cobots), but also increase cognitive stimulation and oversight process while collaborating with technology on this workstation. The new processes will need to carefully consider the changes in the job roles and the subjective perception of human operator and robot responsibilities. The high-level objectives from the human factors point of view are these: (i) decrease of mental fatigue/increase of cognitive engagement with the performed process; (ii) increased satisfaction and motivation working in the particular workstation.

2.4.4. Updates with respect to D1.2

At the beginning, there were three different scenarios which after the consideration and discussions with the consortium members were finalised into a single new process. With this scenario, we will use more human-robot collaboration, achieve acceptable cycle times and obtain results that will positively affect production efficiency in terms of output.

2.4.5. Relation to AI-PRISM

Intelligent and adaptable control station with the cooperation between humans and robots will be developed. The current manual tasks will be conducted either by robot only, human only or both (human and robot). Application of the AI-PRISM robotic solution will increase the resource efficiency (followed by reduction of production costs and increase of production volume) and safety of workers.

The visual control of the product will be done on the first table, and the functional tests on the second table. The first operator will start the process by picking up the product on the conveyor belt and placing it on the first table. As soon as the camera on the robot arm sees that the

product is placed on the first table, it will understand that the product has been placed on the table thanks to the artificial intelligence-based model and object recognition algorithm that has been trained before, and the robot will start the visual control processes. After this process is finished, the operator will take the hood from the first table to the second table. Meanwhile, the first robot will follow the movement of the hood with the artificial intelligence-based real-time object recognition and tracking algorithm with the camera on it, and when it sees that the hood is placed on the second table (or when it sees that the hood is plugged into the socket), it will send the command to the second robot to start working. From this moment on, the first robot will focus on the table in front of it and wait for a new product for visual control. The second robot will continue functional tests. In this way, the product will be followed with the camera footage via the integrated perception of the robot and artificial intelligence, and the two robots will be compatible and synchronized with the changing operation times of the human.

AI-PRISM system will be integrated for tasks such as:

- Object recognition, separation of the hood from other objects in the environment and whether it is in the expected position,
- Real-time object recognition and tracking, real-time tracking of the hood from the first desk to the second desk, and detection of reaching the second desk.

One of the robots will be used for visual control. Industrial camera will be integrated on the robot to provide visual control. A lighting system will be installed in an integrated manner into the camera system. The product to be checked for quality has a metal and glass surface. Therefore, the lighting system is as valuable as the camera choice. Lights falling on the surface may cause errors to escape or cause products that are intact to be evaluated as incorrect. In order to prevent glare of the surface, the lighting will not be directed to the surface directly, and in addition to the solution, it is planned to use a filter on the camera.

Data to be stored and used by artificial intelligence algorithms will be established by the data collection architecture. It will be checked that the hood components are complete and error-free on the collected images.

Error detection on metal and glass surfaces, and the completeness of the components on the hood should be checked. It is planned to use different artificial intelligence models for error detection and object detection on two different surfaces.

Different data sets will be created for artificial intelligence models that will be used for different purposes. Determining the datasets to be created will have a direct impact on the camera's motion route. This will affect the quality control period of the product. The data set to be used in the training of the object detection model that controls the presence of the components is planned to be created from images taken from distant points due to the large sizes of the objects expected to be detected. Due to the small error sizes of the data set to be used in the training of the model for error detection, for these data sets it is planned to be created from images taken from close points. The trained models will be included in the architecture and will perform the quality control function in coordination with the robot.

2.4.6. Specification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Table 4. Indicative list of KPIs

KPI	Description	Validation Metric	Related Task/s, Deliverables	Relation to Objectives	
Social	U4_KPI1	Resource efficiency: 3 human operators to 2 human operators	Increase by 15% (Baseline: 0,75)	T6.1 - T6.3 - T6.4	O1
	U4_KPI2	Total production time :Quality check time	Reduction by 10% (Baseline: 82 sec.)	T4,2 T4.3	O5 - O6
	U4_KPI3	Production cost : human operators number decrease and decrease in cycle time	Reduction by 10% (Baseline: 0,85 EURO)	WP3	O5 - O6
Economic	U4_KPI5	Reduction of cognitive load required from the operator	Reduction by 10% (mental demand assessed with NASA TLX (Hart & Staveland, 1988), and mental effort exhibited on the task would be measured with fNIRS for the validation)	T5.1 - T5.2 - T5.5	O2 -O3

	U4_KPI6	Assess: performance efficiency and job satisfaction	Reduction by 5% (performance efficiency behaviourally coded from the video recordings and triangulated with Occupational self-efficacy (Rigotti et al., 2008) and organizational motivation scale (Cook & Wall, 1980)) (Baseline: 10 sec)	T5.1 - T5.2	O2 -O3
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2.5. Use Case 5: Generic Demonstrator: AI-Control for Natural, Multi-modal Collaboration

2.5.1. Scenario Overview

An overview of the production process of PCBs at KEBA is shown in Figure 43. After PCB production with a SMT line (surface mount technology, Figure 44 right) the non-separated PCBs (shown in in Figure 45 left) are placed in a rolling cart. A human brings the PCBs with the rolling cart to the visual inspection. Significant parts are controlled by eye and the non-separated PCBs are separated manually to single PCBs. The separated PCBs are then packed on trays which are stacked on top of each other on a rolling cart to the testing station. After the testing process the PCBs gets manually transported on a rolling cart to the next work area where the PCBs are assembled.

After a careful initial analysis of the PCB handling Pipeline, the main part of KEBA's AI-Prism use case focuses on the PCB-Testing step, what consist out of 3 Scenarios:

- Scenario 1 PCB handling and testing
- *Scenario 2 Configuring the work-cell for new PCB types: Mounting required testing adapters*
- *Scenario 3 Configuring the work-cell for new PCB types: Handling new PCBs*

The scenarios are split into three for showing the capability of the robotic assistance systems in the production process. Scenario 1 deals with deploying robotic systems as assistive units that can recognize, manipulate and handle different PCBs in the production process. Scenario 2 and Scenario 3 together are structured to better highlight the capability of the system to showcase its easy to configure interfaces in the production process.

Figure 43: PCB production process chain overview at KEBA

Figure 44. AS-IS Step by step diagram of the PCB handling after production; right – station layout currently

Figure 45. Non-separated PCBs (left) and visual inspection (right)

2.5.2. Scenario 1: PCB handling and testing process

2.5.2.1 AS-IS: Process overview

Figure 46 shows a part of the PCB testing area in the production of KEBA nowadays. The stacked boxes with the PCBs are brought to the test station after production (Figure 46 left). An employee prepares the work cell with the correct test adapter for the PCB. After mounting the test adapter, the operator starts loading the correct testing software by scanning the product code. The testing adapter will be opened, then the PCB will be placed in the testing fixture and afterwards the testing adapter will be closed and the software will be started (Figure 46 right). When the testing process is finished, the PCB with successful tests are placed in a box nearby (Figure 46 centre) and the PCB with unsuccessful tests are placed in another box for further handling. There are various types of PCB produced at KEBA, Figure 47 (left) shows two different types of PCBs. The PCBs are stacked side by side as shown in Figure 47 (right).

Figure 46. PCB Testing workplace at the KEBA shop floor

Figure 47. (left) depicts 2 samples from the various type of PCBs produced at KEBA; (right) depicts the pattern of PCBs on a tray stacked on above the other placed on the rolling cart

2.5.2.2 *AS-IS: Step by step decomposition and requirements derivation*

Figure 48 shows the flowchart for the AS-IS step by step decomposition of the PCB testing and handling process.

Pick up PCB. The human picks a PCB from the tray which is nearby the testing station and scans the code on the PCB to choose the right testing procedure for the step, starting test software.

Placing PCB into the test fixture. After taking the PCB by hand the PCB will be placed in the test fixture.

Closing test fixture. Before the test can start the test fixture must be closed.

Starting test software. The human starts the testing software on the computer. After 5s to 30s depending on the testing device, the test fixture can be opened.

Open the test fixture and Taking out PCB. The human opens the test fixture and takes the PCB out of the test fixture by hand.

Deposition to box good/failure parts. After the test is completed the software shows you if the test of the PCB was successful or if a failure occurred. The PCB will be placed on a tray in a box for good or failure parts depending on the test result.

Stack new box. When a certain number of PCBs are reached in a tray a new box will be stacked until a maximum of boxes is reached

Figure 48. Flowchart depicting the AS-IS step by step decomposition of Scenario 1

2.5.2.3 TO-BE: Process overview

As stated in the AS-IS section, the PCBs are currently tested manually. Within the Project AI-Prism, there is the plan to introduce a collaborative robot-assisted PCB testing process. The

idea is to setup a static robotic manipulator in the workstation to handle and test PCBs. The PCBs are placed near the robotic system in the rolling cart. The robotic system should then recognize the various type of PCBs, grasp and manipulate them. The PCBs should be inserted precisely into the testing adapter by the robot and upon successful testing, the PCBs should be placed in a box (in a predefined pattern). In case of PCBs with unsuccessful tests, they should be placed in a separate box for further processing. The work cell is already setup with the required testing adapter and the PCBs for testing are assumed to be placed in stacked trays on a rolling cart near the robot. The robot should then be capable of handling and testing all the PCBs placed in these trays. In case of errors during the process, the robotic system should be equipped with mechanisms to handle them (either by online parametrization of robot tasks or with the help of the user).

Note: This scenario is planned to first be implemented at KEBA innovation lab and evaluated. It will be then demonstrated in the KEBA production plant on successful implementation of the initial setup.

2.5.2.4 *TO-BE: Step by step decomposition*

Figure 49 shows the steps in the PCB handling and testing process.

Robot aided PCB handling and testing process

Step 1: PCB detection

The PCBs are placed in stacked trays on a rolling cart near the robot. The robotic system should be equipped with vision sensors and be able to recognize the PCBs (detect the PCBs and localize the PCBs). The recognition of PCB will follow a model-based approach. The robot should be able to detect multiple different type of PCBs

Step 2: PCB grasping

Once the PCB is recognized (and the pose of the PCB is correctly estimated), the next step is to grasp the PCB and pick it up. For a given PCBs, a set of grasping parameters are assumed to be known a priori (based on configured data). The robot should then physically grasp the PCB based on this grasp parameters. The robot embodiment is equipped with a suitable gripper capable of grasping and manipulating PCBs.

Step 3: PCB pose correction

The main aim for grasping the PCBs is to insert them precisely into the testing adapter to carry out the testing process. However, it can easily happen that the PCBs are grasped inaccurately. This would result in an improper orientation of the PCBs that are grasped by the robot and this might not allow for a precise placement of the PCBs into the testing adapter. Such situation arises due to errors in sensor data or in the grasping process. To alleviate this, the robotic system has to correct the mis alignment of the PCBs by re-orienting them. To perform this operation, the robotic system should first find the current orientation of the PCB (that the robot is currently grasping), compare it with the ideal orientation and then correct the orientation of PCB accordingly for which it is necessary to perform a compensatory movement. Therefore, the robot manipulates the grasped PCB, utilising visual perception, to enable the precise placement of the grasped PCB (in hand) into the testing fixture.

Step 4: Constrained / Precise PCB Placement (into the testing fixture)

Following the manipulation correction guided by vision, the PCB is placed accurately into the testing fixture. Employing force-torque sensing, the system identifies both a successful placement and any potential failure that could lead to damage the PCB. Once the placement is completed, the system confirms the successful placement through visual perception.

Step 5: automated PCB testing

- Testing fixture gets closed automatically
- The PCB testing SW gets started automatically
- Testing fixture gets opened automatically

Step 6: Constrained PCB Pick up out of the testing fixture

After the actual testing procedure finishes, the robot grasps the PCB again that has undergone testing. In scenarios where the test evaluation yields a positive assessment, the robot proceeds to place the PCB onto the tray allocated for PCBs that have passed the test (PCB OK). Alternatively, if the evaluation results negatively, the robot proceeds to deposit the PCB onto the tray assigned for unsuccessful outcomes (PCB NOT OK).

Step 7: Efficient PCB Placement

The last step in the sequence is the robotic task of placing the PCB onto the correct tray. The PCBs should be placed according to an optimal placement pattern for that PCB type. The currently grasped PCB is required to be placed on an unoccupied spot on the tray.

In situations where any of the above steps are not successful, the robotic system initiates communication with a human worker through available communication channels, signalling the requirement for human help for resolving the situation as shown in Figure 50.

Figure 49. Step by Step decomposition flowchart of the PCB handling and testing process

System State Resolving

Within the context of the collaborative workspace involving both human workers and robots, the two entities (worker and robot) collaboratively address the existing (error) state of the system. Consequently, intuitive interfaces for Human-Robot interaction, such as Voice and Graphical User Interface, will be implemented to ensure a quick resolution of the situation and prevent human frustration caused by the system's incomprehensible black-box behaviour. Figure 50 shows the flow of actions during such an error handling process. If the system (robot) is able to resolve the problem, the related strategy will be implemented accordingly for the said process. The different resolution scenarios will be further clarified within Task T4.5. If the system cannot resolve the issue, the user is contacted for further assistance

Figure 50. The flow of actions when an error occurs during the PCB handling and testing process

2.5.3. Scenario 2: Configuring the work-cell for new PCB types: Mounting required testing adapters

2.5.3.1 As-Is: Process overview

When a new PCB is introduced to the production plant, a new testing adapter is required for the new PCB produced in order to test it at the work cell. The worker of the work cell has to fetch the suitable testing adapter, install it to the work cell and then test the new PCB (the PCB testing process is described in 2.5.1.1)

2.5.3.2 *As-Is: Step by step decomposition and requirement derivation*

Scenario 2 is the mounting of the required testing adapter in the work cell. For each PCB a unique testing adapter is needed. The colleague gets the order to mount the PCB adapter with a unique product number on a specified testing station. The human takes the PCB adapter from a storage rack, brings it to the defined testing station and fixes the specified PCB adapter. The workflow is shown in Figure 51.

PCB Testing order:

The human gets the testing order from the resource planning system. In the order it is defined which PCB testing adapter has to be mounted and on which PCB testing station the PCB testing adapter has to be mounted.

Search PCB at Storage Rack:

The PCB testing adapter has a unique number and is placed on a defined place in the storage rack. It will be taken by the human by hand out of the storage rack.

Bring PCB to Testing Station:

The human has taken the testing adapter and brings it manually to the predefined testing station.

Mount PCB adapter in Testing Station:

Each testing station has to be prepared for the next test series. This will be done when the next series is defined which could be immediately done after testing or at a later date.

Figure 51. AS-IS Step by Step decomposition when mounting new testing adapters

2.5.3.3 **TO-BE: Process Overview**

To assist the human in preparing the next work cell, the human interacts with a mobile robot. The task of the mobile robot is to follow the human. After the human has received the next testing order, he can activate the follow-me mode on the AGV, which follows the human step by step into the storage rack. Follow-me mode is activated via a voice interface. After placing

the parts on the mobile robot, it follows the human into the defined work cell. Before the test adapter is assembled, the follow-me mode is deactivated so that the human can take over the test adapter from the AGV. After assembly of the test adapter, the AGV is sent back to a defined location near the storage rack (see Figure 52).

Figure 52. TO BE: The envisioned step by step decomposition when mounting new testing adapters

2.5.3.4 TO-BE: Step by step decomposition

PCB Testing order:

The human gets the testing order from the resource planning system and goes to the shortage rack.

Enable Follow me mode at AGV:

Nearby the storage rack is an AGV waiting for commands. To enable the follow me mode there is a voice interface implemented at the AGV. After enabling the follow me mode the AGV follows the human and stops if the AGV is too close to the human.

Look for specified testing adapter:

Each testing adapter has a unique number. The human knows the number for the next testing adapter from the planning system.

Place testing adapter on AGV:

The human gives the AGV the command to wait that the person can place the PCB testing adapter at the AGV. The follow me mode is still enabled.

Walk to defined testing station:

After placing the test adapter, the human can enable the follow me mode again. Afterwards, the person will go to the testing station which has to be prepared.

Disable follow me mode:

The AGV will stay at the same position when the follow me mode will be disabled.

Take testing adapter from AGV:

The human takes the prepared PCB testing adapter from the AGV

Mount testing adapter:

The human mounts the PCB testing adapter in the testing station and prepares it for the next testing series.

Send AGV back to storage rack:

With a voice command to go back the AGV drives to a defined position near the storage rack.

2.5.4. ***Scenario 3: Configuring the work-cell for new PCB types: Handling new PCBs***

2.5.4.1 ***As-Is: Process overview***

When a new PCB is introduced to the plant, the suitable testing adapter is configured at the workcell as described in Section 2.5.3.1. The worker then follows the same steps as described in 2.5.2.1 to handle the PCB, since the sequence of handling a new PCB is the same apart from requiring the suitable testing adapter.

2.5.4.2 ***As-Is: Step by step decomposition and requirement derivation***

The same steps as mentioned in Section 2.5.3.2 are carried out for human workers to handle new PCBs.

2.5.4.3 ***TO-BE: Process Overview***

The objective is to provide an easy to use interface for the user to easily configure the robotic system to handle and test PCBs when a new type of PCB is introduced to the production plant.

The various tasks required to handle and test a PCB by the robotic system are as mentioned in Section 2.5.2.4. However, there is not pre-configured data available for the newly introduced PCB. Each of these tasks requires parameterization for PCBs in a general context and especially for each newly introduced PCB type. Therefore, various channels for interaction between humans and robots are introduced. Possible options include a voice-centric interface, interaction based on graphical user interface, and kinaesthetic teaching. The Interactive Teach in process could start with the human placing the PCB into the Testing Adapter.

Figure 53. Different modalities to exploit for the interactive interface to program robots

2.5.4.4 **TO-BE: Step by step decomposition**

The following individual steps propose methods to configure the essential robotic tasks involved in the robot aided PCB testing (Scenario 1) utilising different human robot interfaces.

PCB Detection

The human co-worker will configure the perception system of the robot for the detection process through one of the suggested modalities. The initial idea is to develop an interactive GUI that provides the Human a view of the systems understanding of the workplace. By integrating the Human into the loop and considering the feedback, the system can further improve the understanding of the workplace.

PCB Grasping

The human co-worker will configure the perception system of the robot for the grasping process through one of the suggested modalities. The initial idea is utilising the programming by demonstration paradigm or use an image-based interaction methodology for parametrizing a suitable grasping point on the PCB. Alternatively, the system could propose appropriate grasping points for the PCB to the human. Again, the feedback of the human could improve the AI based algorithms.

PCB Pose Correction, precise PCB placement into testing fixture, static PCB pickup out of the testing fixture

The human co-worker will configure the perception system of the robot for the processes through one or more of the suggested modalities. An initial concept includes the utilisation of a voice interface to trigger and control collection of essential data of the PCB that is required for accurately positioning the PCBs of the same type within the testing fixture during operation.

Efficient PCB placement

This step concerns itself with bin packing where the goal is to efficiently place the tested PCBs on a tray in the box. The initial idea involves suggesting an efficient pattern to the human through a GUI and capitalise on the human expertise utilising their feedback to further improve the systems capabilities.

Note: It is not envisioned to develop programming interfaces for all the processes mentioned above. The intention is to mention the possibility of tasks where the programming interfaces could aid the user in easily configuring the robotic process. The final chosen interfaces (clarified within T4.5) and the related process steps will depend further on the technical feasibility, potential impact on KPIs and user acceptance.

2.5.5. Key Human Factors

The PCB testing AS-IS process is illustrated by a quick turnaround rate for each PCB, however, with experience, the operators perform this process without experiencing increased temporal demand as revealed by interviewing the operator. The repetitive nature of the task and a quick pace of the process, however, emphasize the potential for increased mental fatigue. The

operator interview about the process (D5.1) outlined the importance of self-efficacy and learning new skills. These aspects should be incorporated in the task and carefully introduced in the operator training programme and the new process descriptions. Furthermore, working with the new technology would provide upskilling and organizational development opportunities which could enhance satisfaction with the task and organizational commitment. The high-level objectives from the human factors point of view are these: (i) decrease of mental fatigue/increase of cognitive engagement with the performed process; (ii) increased self-efficacy and motivation working in the particular workstation.

2.5.6. Updates with respect to D1.2

The use case has evolved when compared to the initial version mentioned in D1.2. Only the robotic assistance system to handle and test PCBs was proposed. This is now extended to include three scenarios, where the first scenario still deals with the robotic assistance systems to handle PCBs and is now also includes an error handling. The other two scenarios deal with developing and implementing multi-modal interfaces to configure the production process. Development will focus on implementing interfaces to ease the user effort in configuring the work cell. A mobile platform is envisioned to follow the user (in a follow me mode) to assist the user in setting up new testing adapters required for the testing of new PCBs. Multi-modal interfaces are also developed to ease the programming effort of configuring robotic systems in the work-cell for handling new PCB types.

2.5.7. Relation to AI-PRISM

The KEBA use case focuses on different scenarios. The different scenarios relate to AI-Prism project by teaching the robot, an easy to use interface for humans and different human machine interfaces for collaboration.

2.5.8. Specification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Table 5: Indicative list of KPIs

	KPI	Description	Validation Metric	Related Task/s, Deliverables	Relation to Objectives
Social	U5_KPI1	A Mobile AGV following and assisting the user	Improved acceptance of the new interfaces ((System usability scale (Brooke, 1995) 80% acceptance; Technology acceptance model 3questionnaire (Venkatesh V, Bala H (2008); Occupational self-efficacy (Rigotti et al., 2008); Technology Readiness Scale (Rose & Fogarty, 2010)	WP4, WP5	O3, O4
	U5 KPI2	The mental load experienced during training phase.	20% decrease in time needed to be trained on the new process and 10% decrease in mental and temporal demands during the initial stages of working on the new system (as measured by NASA TLX ((Hart & Staveland, 1988))	WP4, WP5	O4, O5, O6
Economic	U5 KPI3	The setup time required to configure the robot, as compared to traditional methods.	Reduced by 12%	WP4	O4, O6
	U5 KPI4	Number of Human Robot Interaction modalities for configuring the robot to a complex task.	Min. 2 modalities used concurrently	WP3, WP4	O3, O4, O5, O6
	U5 KPI6	The level of technical knowledge required by users for operating and training.	Non-Robot process experts can easily use the training system	WP4 , WP5	O4, O5
	U5 KPI 7	The duration needed to train a non-expert user.	Reduced by 20%	WP4, WP5	O4, O5
Note: The references to the questionnaire are given in Annex B of this document					

3. Methodology for Requirement Specifications and Analysis

The methodology for formalization of the requirements specifications include the following steps

- Elicitation of functional and non-functional user requirements, constraints and applied standards/regulations, on the way of the interviews (surveys) with the users, use case

scenarios analyses, original project vision and specialised literature review. It should result in the stakeholder requirements (for more details see Section 3.1)

- Analysis of the stakeholder requirements, which leads to the definition and the specification of system requirements (for more details see Section 3.2)

3.1. Stakeholder Requirement Elicitation

The requirements definition process begins with the elicitation of stakeholder requirements. It is a complex process that consists of gathering, researching, defining, structuring, and clarifying a product's requirements. The actions needed during the requirements elicitation process have been illustrated in Figure 54.

Figure 54. Requirement specification process

The first step of preparation for requirements elicitation is to understand the elicitation activity scope and to identify the stakeholders from whom those requirements are to be gathered. It is common in requirements engineering to define a stakeholder as someone who has a stake in the project—that is, someone who is involved in or affected by the project in some way, or can affect the project in some way and therefore are interested in its success. Next should be selected the right techniques for gathering the requirements. Gathering the requirements is a big part of the elicitation process and it might take a lot of time and effort to uncover all of the primary requirements from all of the stakeholder's requirements. It's quite possible to elicit many of these requirements from marketing experts and analysts who can obtain many requirements from a representative body. Other methods of capturing stakeholder requirements can include focus groups or conducting either individual or group interviews with process experts or even workers. Following the results of the user surveys and interviews, the next step of our approach concerns the categorization and prioritization of the gathered requirements. In this scope, the assessed user requirements should first be organized in specific categories, called:

- i. **functional** (description of the system functions or tasks to be performed, usually obtained through use cases analysis),
- ii. **non-functional** (specification of the quality attributes of the system),
- iii. **constraint** (limitation of the options open to a designer of a solution by imposing immovable boundaries and limits),
- iv. **normative** (applied standards/regulations).

For each category, a requirements prioritization analysis should be performed, so as to specify the importance value:

- i. Must have (requirements that are critical to meeting the project's objectives),
- ii. Should (requirements that are critical and should be included if possible, but which can be excluded),
- iii. Could (requirements that are part of the project's scope and add or enhance project benefits),
- iv. Would (requirements that do not have a significant impact on project benefits or could be considered as a "would like to have").

Finally, the stakeholder requirements gathered in the elicitation session/s and collected in the table (for example see Table 6) are checked for accuracy.

3.2. Mapping of Stakeholder Requirements to System Requirements

The workflow for mapping the stakeholder requirements into the fundamental structures in terms of hardware, human robot collaboration, AI enhancing tools and Social Collaboration requirements is shown in Figure 55. The mapping is then extended to map the gathered system requirements to the system components (Note: only a selection of the system components are visualized in the Figure 55).

Figure 55. Requirements Mapping from Stakeholder requirements to system requirements and to System components

3.3. Technology Pull Vs Technology Push

The refinement of the use case definitions and the mapping of stakeholder requirements to system requirements is supported on a Technology Pull / Technology Push methodology involving all relevant stakeholders to promote mutual understanding to use case definition and alignment. The methodology consisted on the following steps:

1. **Technology Push Phase:** In this initial phase, technology providers analyzed the initial as-is and to-be use case descriptions documented in the previous iteration of this deliverable, and provided an initial mapping of technological components to use cases and specific requirements, further detailing how the functionalities and capabilities of each component contribute to the use case implementation. Technology providers also foresee specific validation methodologies, describing how these can be validated in each use case. The result is an initial technology push mapping describing how each component can be used and validated in each scenario which is presented and discussed with use case owners in meetings.

1. **Technology Pull Phase:** Subsequently, use case owners and technical leaders digest the result of the technology pull phase. They refine the use case descriptions by incorporating the technological insights, ensuring that there are no functional gaps, overlaps, or discrepancies. This phase facilitates a bilateral refinement of the TO-BE scenarios, adjusting the initial definition of scenarios and requirements.
2. **Agreement on Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs):** All stakeholders collaboratively agree upon the target TRLs for each technological component. This establishes a mutual understanding of the expected maturity level. In this process, the different use case pilots are analysed as a whole, to make sure that they are complementary and that all piloting activities jointly address the overarching project objectives and planning.

The outcome of the exercise is a comprehensive mapping of technical components to use cases, with aligned expectations on functionalities and readiness levels. This mapping provides the foundation for the definition of the to-be scenarios that will guide the implementation phase. While not explicitly stated, the feedback loops between stakeholders will be maintained during the implementation phase, to ensure that system requirements are adequately updated. The process encourages bi-directional communication between technology providers and use case owners and allows for early identification of limitations, constraints of functional gaps.

4. Requirement Analysis

The different requirements (stakeholder requirements, hardware requirements, human robot collaboration requirements, AI enhancing tools requirements and Social collaboration requirements) for the five use cases in AI-PRISM are given in the ANNEX A. Since these requirements are already given in D1.2 and there have not been many changes, these requirement tables have been moved to ANNEX A for a better readability.

4.1. Use Case 1: Furniture

4.1.1. Mapping Pilot Requirements to Technical Components

Table 6. Mapping of requirements to technical components

<u>Pilot requirements</u>	<u>Technical Component</u>	<u>Responsible</u> *	<u>Acceptance Criteria</u>	<u>Target TRL*</u>
<u>Create Work Schedule</u> (USt R1; U1HR R.1.4.1; U1HR R1.2.1 U1AI R2.1.1, U1AI R2.1.2, U1AI R2.1.4, U1AI R2.1.2, U1AI R2.1.4,	AI-PRISM AI-based Ambient Level Reasoning Enhancing Modules	IT1	<u>To generate the work schedule, reasoning modules must access necessary data from the company's ERP (e.g., due dates, bill of materials, warehouse status, etc.) and other pertinent information systems. Using this data, the modules must generate weekly work order plans, incorporating the training of the painting robot. As the plan is executed, ambient level reasoning must monitor work order progress and respond</u>	<u>TRL 5 to 7</u>

			to unexpected situations identified in the ambient or from other information sources (e.g., the ERP).	
<u>Work Order Execution Control</u> (U1St R5; U1HR R.1.4.1; U1HR R.1.4.2; U1HR R.1.4.3; U1HR R.1.4.5; U1HR R1.2.3; U1SC R5)	AI-PRISM AI-based Ambient Level Reasoning Enhancing Modules	UPV (CIGIP)	Reasoning modules user interfaces must enable experienced workers to verify the performance of the robot's painting program using key performance indicators, aiding in assessing program efficiency and resource use. At change-over, reasoning modules UIs must display product details and work order information, including materials, equipment configuration, and manual instructions. Upon worker confirmation, ambient level reasoning interfaces with the painting line control software to set parameters. It uses work-in-progress data to monitor work order progress, ensuring the correct robot painting program is always used. The worker conducts a quality check through the interface, and the results, linked to the production order, are stored for future reference and analysis.	TRL 5 to 7
<u>Ambient perception</u> (U1HR R.1.1.4; U1St R9; U1AI R1.2.2	AI-PRISM AI-based Perception Enhancing Modules	FBK	AI-based perception enhancing modules process the real time digital model of the scene to detect errors in piece position at the beginning of the process, before starting painting.	TRL 5 to 7
<u>Ambient digitalization</u> (U1St R8; U1St R9; U1AI R1.2.2	AI-PRISM Ambient Digitalisation Modules	FBK	Ambient digitalisation modules apply synchronisation mechanisms to reconstruct a real-time digital model of the collaboration ambient based on the data gathered from the ambient sensing infrastructure.	TRL 6 to 7

<p><u>Ambient Sensing</u> (U1HR R.1.1.4; U1St R8; U1St R11; U1AI R1.2.1)</p>	<p><u>AI-PRISM Ambient sensing infrastructure</u></p>	<p><u>FBK</u></p>	<p><u>Several sensors will be installed on the painting cabin to collectively monitor the ambient conditions for safety and quality purposes.</u></p>	<p><u>TRL 6 to 7</u></p>
<p><u>Applying Paint and Moving the Frame</u> (U1St R6; U1St R7; U1SC R4)</p>	<p><u>AI-PRISM Base Hardware</u></p>	<p><u>UPV (AI2)</u></p>	<p><u>The execution for the painting program involves a single 6-axis collaborative manipulator robots equipped with a precise painting tool, and a PLC controller that is interconnected through an actuator with the base of the frame, allowing it to rotate it.</u></p>	<p><u>TRL 6 to 9</u></p>
<p><u>Data Persistence and Access</u> (U1SC R1; U1SC R2; U1SC R3)</p>	<p><u>AI-PRISM Data Platform</u></p>	<p><u>Wings</u></p>	<p><u>The AI-PRISM Data Platform persists the execution process monitoring information collected by the IIoT Platform. This ensures that crucial data related to the painting process is persisted for future reference and analysis.</u></p>	<p><u>TRL 7 to 9</u></p>
<p><u>Execution Process Real-Time Monitoring</u> (U1St R8; U1St R9)</p>	<p><u>AI-PRISM IIoT Platform</u></p>	<p><u>Wings</u></p>	<p><u>The IIoT Platform gathers real-time data from the conveyor and each frame's position through the Finiture software, providing reliable information on the painting line's status and progress. It also collects real-time data from ambient sensing infrastructure, perception modules, and the painting robot, enabling adaptation of the robot painting to the ambient situation.</u></p>	<p><u>TRL 6 to 8</u></p>
<p><u>Programming by Example for Robot Painting Program in the Test Cell</u> (U1St R2; U1St R3; U1St R4; U1HR R.1.1.1; U1HR R.1.1.2; U1HR R.1.1.3; U1HR R.1.1.4;</p>	<p><u>AI-PRISM Programming by Demonstration Environment</u></p>	<p><u>UPV (AI2)</u></p>	<p><u>The test cell is equipped with the same hardware as the robotic painting cells: A robotic arm equipped with a painting tool and connected to a PLC that senses the rotation of the frame where the pieces of furniture are placed, and RGBD cameras to sense the ambient. The experienced worker demonstrates how to paint the chair using the programming by demonstration hardware: Oculus</u></p>	<p><u>TRL 5 to 7</u></p>

<p><u>U1HR R.1.3.1;</u> <u>U1HR R.1.3.2;</u> <u>U1SC R5; U1SC R6)</u></p>			<p><u>controllers. Together with the sensing infrastructure, the programming by demonstration hardware captures the details of the painting tool's trajectories, movements, and the positions of the painting tool and the furniture piece.</u></p>	
<p><u>Real time communications</u> <u>(U1SC R1; U1SC R2;</u> <u>U1SC R3)</u></p>	<p><u>AI-PRISM Real Time Communications Network</u></p>	<p><u>ITI</u></p>	<p><u>Low latency communication between the air quality sensors and Ambient Digitalisations modules.</u></p>	<p><u>TRL 5 to 7</u></p>
<p><u>ROS distributed communications for seamless connectivity</u> <u>(U1St R10; U1SC R3;</u> <u>U1AI R1.2.1)</u></p>	<p><u>AI-PRISM ROS Framework</u></p>	<p><u>IKER</u></p>	<p><u>ROS acts a robust communication platform, enabling interactions between different modules of AI-PRISM. All captured required for hard time critical systems is available in the ROS distributed communication network, then bridged to the IIoT Platform to facilitate reliable communications between the robotic system and higher-level (soft time critical) modules.</u></p>	<p><u>TRL 5 to 7</u></p>
<p><u>Responsive Robot Painting</u> <u>(U1St R8; U1St R9)</u></p>	<p><u>AI-PRISM AI-based Agent Level Reasoning Enhancing Modules</u></p>	<p><u>KUL</u></p>	<p><u>The robot must monitor its surroundings through collected tracking data, including the furniture being painted and potential environmental changes. Utilizing this information, the agent level reasoning module dynamically modifies the robot's painting program, adjusting the robotic arm movements and frame rotation control. This guarantees accuracy and efficiency in the painting process, even when encountering unforeseen circumstances.</u></p>	<p><u>TRL 5 to 7</u></p>

4.2. Use Case 2: Reduction of environmental pollution with waste from production of semiconductors

4.2.1. Mapping Pilot Requirements to Technical Components

Table 7. Mapping of requirements to technical components

Pilot requirements	Technical Component	Responsible	Acceptance Criteria	Target TRL
U3St_R1, U3St_R3, U3St_R6	AI-PRISM ROS Framework	IKE	All systems must use the ROS middleware	8
U3St_R1, U3St_R3, U3St_R5, U3St_R6, U3St_R7, U3H_R1.1.1, U3H_R2.1.1, U3H_R2.1.2, U3H_R2.1.3, U3H_R2.2.1, U3SC_R1	AI-PRISM Base Hardware	UPV	Robots must be able to move the appropriate weight loads	8
U3St_R1, U3St_R3, U3St_R6	AI-PRISM Communications Modules	IKE	All systems must use the ROS middleware	8
U3H_R1.1.1, U3H_R4.1	AI-PRISM Ambient sensing infrastructure	FBK	RGB-D cameras must collect robust color 3D information	6 to 8
U3St_R10	AI-PRISM IIoT Platform	WIN	All systems must connect to the platform to exchange data	8
U3St_R10	AI-PRISM Data Platform	WIN	All systems must retrieve data when needed	8
Required by "AI-PRISM AI-based Perception Enhancing Modules"	AI-PRISM Ambient Digitalization Modules	FBK	Robust color 3D reconstruction	6 to 8
U3St_R2, U3St_R4, U3AI_R1.2.1	AI-PRISM AI-based Perception Enhancing Modules	FBK	Coordinates of sacks and bottles are produced	6 to 8
U3St_R8, U3H_R1.1.1, U3AI_R1.1.1	AI-PRISM Human Safety Management Procedures	NTTData Italy	Safety is guaranteed at all events	8

4.3. Use Case 3: Brewery/Food industry transformation towards Industry 5.0

4.3.1. Mapping Pilot Requirements to Technical Components

Table 8. Mapping of requirements to technical components

Pilot requirements	Technical Component	Responsible	Acceptance Criteria	Target TRL
U3St_R1, U3St_R3, U3St_R6	AI-PRISM ROS Framework	IKE	All systems must use the ROS middleware	8
U3St_R1, U3St_R3, U3St_R5, U3St_R6, U3St_R7, U3H_R1.1.1, U3H_R2.1.1, U3H_R2.1.2, U3H_R2.1.3, U3H_R2.2.1, U3SC_R1	AI-PRISM Base Hardware	UPV	Robots must be able to move the appropriate weight loads	8
U3St_R1, U3St_R3, U3St_R6	AI-PRISM Communications Modules	IKE	All systems must use the ROS middleware	8
U3H_R1.1.1, U3H_R4.1	AI-PRISM Ambient sensing infrastructure	FBK	RGB-D cameras must collect robust color 3D information	6 to 8
U3St_R10	AI-PRISM IIoT Platform	WIN	All systems must connect to the platform to exchange data	8
U3St_R10	AI-PRISM Data Platform	WIN	All systems must retrieve data when needed	8
Required by "AI-PRISM AI-based Perception Enhancing Modules"	AI-PRISM Ambient Digitalization Modules	FBK	Robust color 3D reconstruction	6 to 8
U3St_R2, U3St_R4, U3AI_R1.2.1	AI-PRISM AI-based Perception Enhancing Modules	FBK	Coordinates of sacks and bottles are produced	6 to 8
U3St_R8, U3H_R1.1.1, U3AI_R1.1.1	AI-PRISM Human Safety Management Procedures	NTTData Italy	Safety is guaranteed at all events	8

4.4. Use Case 4: Adaptable & Collaborative Workstation

4.4.1. Mapping Pilot Requirements to Technical Components

Table 9. Mapping of requirements to technical components

Pilot requirements	Technical Component	Responsible*	Acceptance Criteria	Target TRL*
Defect Detection	AI-based Perception	TEKNOPAR, SIL	An automated and efficient system that utilizes visual data from cameras or sensors to identify and detect defects or anomalies in manufactured products or objects.	TRL6 to TRL7
Programming the robotic system to handle different process steps	AI-based Perception, Agent Level Reasoning, Acting and Control	TEKNOPAR, SIL, COMAU	The cobot will do functional tests (included engine functional levels and propeller crack checks) and visual inspection.	TRL4 to TRL7
Object recognition	AI-based Perception, Agent Level Reasoning, Acting and Control	TEKNOPAR, SIL	Distinguishing the hood from other objects in the environment, and verifying whether the hood is in the expected position.	TRL5 to TRL7
Human Experiments	Simulation environment	TEKNOPARK, SIL, TAU	Operators availability to perform experiments and collect data in order to test and validate SE algorithms	TRL6 to TRL7

Production information	Simulation environment	TEKNOPARK, SIL	Production data (order information, organization information, operation information and worker information). Including product and scenario 3D representations and, robotic visualization with behavioural modules.	TRL6 to TRL7
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4.5. Use Case 5 : Generic Demonstrator

4.5.1. Mapping Pilot Requirements to Technical Components

Table 10. Mapping of requirements to technical components

Pilot requirements	Technical Component	Responsible*	Acceptance Criteria	Target TRL*
Detection and Manipulation of multiple PCBs (U5St_R1, U5St_R3)	AI-based Perception, Agent Level Reasoning, Acting and Control	FBK, KUL, PRO, KEBA	The system is able to detect multiple (at least 4) PCB types; The system is able to grasp and manipulate multiple PCB types	TRL 6 to 7
Programming the robotic system to handle different process steps (recognition, grasping, pose correction, object placement) (U5St_R2, U5St_R11, U5St_R6, U5St_R19)	Learning from Human Demonstration and Human-Robot Interaction	KUL, KEBA, PRO	The programming interface can configure/teach the robot (at least two process steps)	TRL 6 to 7
Configuring the robotic work cell (U5St_R2, U5St_R11, U5St_R6, U5St_R19, U5St_R2, U5St_R11, U5St_R6, U5St_R35)	Learning from Human Demonstration and Human-Robot Interaction	KUL, KEBA, PRO	Implementing multi-modal interface to configure the robotic work cell	TRL 6 to 7
Mobile manipulator capable of follow me	AI-based Perception, Ambient Level and	UPV, KEBA	The AGV should follow the user	TRL 5 to 6

(following the user) mode (U5St_R27, U5St_R28, U5St_R6)	Agent Level Reasoning Acting and Control		around and respond to user commands	
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5. Conclusion

The present deliverable reports the efforts done in the scope of the T1.3 and T1.4 of the AI-PRISM project toward the definition of the use cases and the requirement analysis specifications of the AI-PRISM system. On the basis of the user requirements and use cases, and after clarifying the overall system purpose and perimeter, a functional analysis of the AI-PRISM system was performed towards identifying the necessary requirements (Hardware, Human Robot Collaboration aspects, the required AI Enhancing tools and the social collaboration aspects) that should be established in respect to each use case and related user requirements. This deliverable is an updated version of D1.2 Use cases scenarios and requirements analysis (I) submitted in M6.

This work allowed the consortium to elaborate the requirement, hardware, and software requirements on the basis of user requirements and foreseen use cases. It also enabled to prioritize the functional (and non-functional) requirements and subsequently the technical specifications (which will be dealt in detail in D2.2) that should be implemented, by building upon the prioritization of user requirements and use cases. Based on this set of prioritized functional specifications, the implementation plan of the AI-PRISM project shall build upon, toward ensuring both that high priority use cases will be the first ones to be addressed from the project developments, as well as that project developments will maintain a clear orientation toward the most important user needs and expectations.

Finally, it should be stated that although the present deliverable has been drafted according to the AI-PRISM DoA in the first twelve months of the project, the hardware components and their specifications will remain an open issue until all components and subsystems are built and all modules have been integrated to establish the final, AI-PRISM robotic platform. In the following, the deliverable D1.3 will serve as the basis for further system developments. Specifically, the hardware development is starting with several feasibility studies in order to deliver the first version of the AI-PRISM robotic platform according to the plan drafted within DoA.

ANNEX A: Requirements

The different requirements (stakeholder requirements, hardware requirements, human robot collaboration requirements, AI enhancing tools requirements and Social collaboration requirements) for the five use cases in AI-PRISM are given below.

5.1. Use Case 1: Furniture

5.1.1. Stakeholder Requirements

Table 11. Stakeholder requirements

ID	Category	Priority	Criterion	Specification
U1St_R1	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must get the information it requires (eg. product identifiers, product colour, shape, material) from corporate software (Finiture or SAP) as well as robot
U1St_R2	Functional	Must	Operational	Cobot must learn painting and sanding new products based on few examples provided by a specialist
U1St_R3	Functional	Must	Operational	The cobot must be able to learn and perform the painting and sanding processes for different shapes, group of colors, and wood types
U1St_R4	Functional	Must	Operational	Robot programming by example must be intuitive, the operator must be able to program the robot performing the operation (painting or sanding) on a sample product (either physical or virtual)
U1St_R5	Functional	Must	Operational	The cobot must work under human supervision, the operator needs to confirm the actions to be performed by the robot
U1St_R6	Functional	Must	Mobility	The cobot must be able to paint pieces of furniture in the three positions of the frame, change from one position to another, and turn the frame in the horizontal axis

U1St_R7	Functional	Must	Operational	The cobot must be able to paint all pieces of furniture that do not need to be turned vertically and those that, when turned vertically manually by an operator, are fixed to the frame in a stable position
U1St_R8	Functional	Must	Safety	The cobot must stop or adapt the operation speed when operators are within safety distance
U1St_R9	Functional	Must	Perception	The cobot must be able to perceive the properties of the piece of furniture that needs to be painted or sanded (colour and shape)
U1St_R10	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must use intuitive visual and/or accousting interfaces to alert and communicate with operators
U1St_R11	Functional	Must	Perception	The digitalization system must install ambient data sensors to ensure optimal conditions for painting and worker safety.
U1St_R12	Functional	Must	Perception	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different cameras to recreate the 3D space
U1St_R13	Functional	Must	Perception	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different sensor to measure the working environment
U1St_R14	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must include an interface to allow the user to deploy the convenient container into the desired device
U1St_R15	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must include an interface to allow the user to monitor the state of the network between the different devices
U1St_R16	Functional	Must	Operational	The cobot must only start if alerts generated have been attended to or closed previously
U1St_R17	Functional	Must	Operational	User interfaces must be responsive and adapt to different end user devices
U1St_R18	Functional	Should	Operational	The system must have full traceability of product, LOT ID reading, etc.

U1St_R19	Constraint	Must	Safety	Communication with MES, operational time, parameters, LOT ID, other parameters to be saved in MES
U1St_R20	Constraint	Must	Other	All solution must comply with the machinery directive and do not harm the operator
U1St_R21	Functional	Would	Operational	The system must comply with Clean Room ISO 8 requirements
U1St_R22	Functional	Should	Operational	The robot equipped with low force sensor to prevent harming operators or damaging any physical object
U1St_R23	Functional	Would	Operational	The system should be able to manage priority of operations based on operator presence in working areas.
U1St_R24	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be compatible with the specified robots
U1St_R25	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide an interface to start and stop a new training sample
U1St_R26	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide interfaces to validate the results of the training, providing feedback on the performance of the operation learned (e.g. cycle time, materials used, compared to actual baselines)
U1St_R27	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the evolution of performance KPIs
U1St_R28	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to monitor performance indicators for the current production order (e.g. mean cycle time, cycle time histogram, paint used, OEE)
U1St_R29	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be able to rebuild the 3D Space
U1St_R30	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to configure and verify the connection to other corporate software (SAP or Finiture)
U1St_R32	Normative	Must	Safety	The robot application should meet the normative requirements for

				collaborative robots according to ISO/TS 15066:2016
U1St_R33	Normative	Must	Operational	The system must be able to model and store the sequence of movements performed by the operator during cobot training

5.1.2. System level requirements specification for hardware

Table 12. System-level requirements specification for hardware

ID	Requirement Source	Priority	Requirement
U1H_R1	Robot System General		
U1H_R1.1	U1St_R1	High	The robot must be able to connect to the services necessary to obtain the date and time
U1H_R2	Manipulator		
U1H_R2.1	General		
U1H_R2.1.1	U1St_R7	High	6-axis collaborative manipulator robots with a minimum payload of 10kg and a minimum reach of 1000 mm. (One for painting and one for sanding)
U1H_R2.2	Gripper		
U1H_R2.2.1	U1St_R7	High	A tool that can be mounted on the manipulator robot and used to paint the wood
U1H_R2.2.2	U1St_R7	High	A tool that can be mounted on the manipulator robot and is able to sand
U1H_R3	Network Infrastructure		
U1H_R3.1	U1St_R1	High	Connectivity to network time services, OT (Finiture), or IT (SAP)
U1H_R3.2	U1St_R1	High	The Cobot shall be equipped with at least 1 communication port. (Ethernet, wifi)
U1H_R3.3	U1St_R1	High	The physical layer should have a bandwidth of 1 GB for wired network.

U1H_R3.4	U1St_R1	High	The physical layer should have a latency < 5 ms for the wired and <20 ms for wireless network.
U1H_R3.5	U1St_R11	High	Wireless suspended ambient and particle monitoring for each cabin (Staining, coating, finishing and sanding).
U1H_R3.6	U1St_R11	High	Wireless systems must have a sufficient range to cover the entire industrial facility and enable reliable communication between devices.
U1H_R3.7	U1St_R11	Medium	Wireless devices must be able to operate for extended periods without the need for battery replacement or other maintenance.
U1H_R3.8	Derived	Medium	Capability to obtain real-time data from the process control area at line and workstation level.
U1H_R3.9	Derived	High	The communication system must allow for remote access to industrial devices and equipment from external locations, enabling remote monitoring and control of AI-PRISM components.
U1H_R4	Perception Sensors		
U1H_R4.1	U1St_R10	High	RGBD cameras (3 to obtain piece position and 2 for human detection)
U1H_R4.2	U1St_R7	High	In the sanding process, it is necessary to control the applied force, so a force sensor is needed.
U1H_R4.3	U1St_R6	Medium	2 laser scanners to detect human proximity (1 for sanding and 1 for painting)
U1H_R5	Equipment		
U1H_R5.1	U1St_R10	High	The illumination of the environment must be controlled, for which light panels are needed.

U1H_R5.2	Derived	Medium	A PLC is needed to control the different elements of the system.
U1H_R5.3	U1St_R8	Medium	To move the robot between the three frames, a railway and a robot base is needed.
U1H_R5.4	U1St_R10	Medium	Embedded system for connecting cameras

5.1.3. System level requirements specification for Human-Robot Collaboration

Table 13. System-level requirements specification for Human-Robot Collaboration

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U1HR_R1	Human Robot Interactive Interfaces		
U1HR_R1.1	General		
U1HR_R.1.1.1	User interfaces must provide visual alerts to warn users of errors	Medium	U1St_R10
U1HR_R.1.1.2	The cobot must only start if alerts generated have been attended to or closed previously	High	U1St_R10, U1St_R16
U1HR_R.1.1.3	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different cameras to recreate the 3D space	Medium	U1St_R12
U1HR_R.1.1.4	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different sensor to measure the working environment	Medium	U1St_R13

U1HR_R.1.1.5	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the current status of the cobot (eg. whether it is operating or not, what is the current production order, what is the status of the process)	Medium	U1St_R10
U1HR_R.1.1.6	The system must include an interface to allow the user to deploy the convenient container into the desired device	Medium	U1St_R14
U1HR_R.1.1.7	The cobot must only start if alerts generated have been attended to or closed previously	Medium	U1St_R10
U1HR_R.1.1.8	User interfaces must be responsive and adapt to different end user devices	Medium	U1St_R17
U1HR_R.1.1.9	The system must have full traceability of product, LOT ID reading, etc.	Medium	U1St_R18
U1HR_R.1.1.10	Communication with MES, operational time, parameters, LOT ID, other parameters to be saved in MES	Medium	U1St_R19
U1HR_R1.2	Configuration Interface		
U1HR_R.1.2.1	The system must provide user interfaces to configure and verify the connection to other	Low	U1St_R1

	corporate software (SAP or Finiture)		
U1HR_R.1.2.2	The system must provide user interfaces to select which product references will be integrated, out of all the existing references in the corporate software (SAP or Finiture)	Medium	U1St_R30
U1HR_R1.3	Training		
U1HR_R.1.3.1	The system must be able to model and store the sequence of movements performed by the operator during cobot training	High	U1St_R33
U1HR_R.1.3.2	The system must provide an interface to start and stop a new training sample for a piece of furniture (shape, colour group, and wood type)	Medium	U1St_R25
U1HR_R.1.3.3	The system must provide interfaces to validate the results of the training, providing feedback on the performance of the operation learned (e.g. cycle time, materials used, compared to actual baselines)	Low	U1St_R26
U1HR_R1.4	Operations Control		

U1HR_R.1.4.1	The system must provide user interfaces to confirm the current production order and product information (colour, shape, wood type). If the operator does not confirm the robot will not perform any operation.	Medium	U1St_R10
U1HR_R.1.4.2	The system must provide user interfaces to monitor performance indicators for the current production order (e.g. mean cycle time, cycle time histogram, paint used, OEE)	Low	U1St_R28
U1HR_R.1.4.3	The system must alert the operator if there is an error during an operation	Medium	U1St_R10
U1HR_R.1.4.4	The system must alert the operator when it has finalised an operation step that requires manual intervention (e.g. turn a piece of furniture manually)	Medium	U1St_R10
U1HR_R.1.5	Performance Monitoring		
U1HR_R.1.5.1	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the evolution of performance KPIs	Low	U1St_R27
U1HR_R.1.5.2	The system must include an interface to allow the user to	Low	U1St_R15

	monitor the state of the network between the different devices		
U1HR_R2	Portability of Solution		
U1HR_2.1	General		
U1HR_R2.1.1	The system must be compatible with the specified robots		U1St_R24
U1HR_R3	Robot Manipulation		
U1HR_R3.1	General		
U1HR_R3.1.1	Cobot must learn painting and sanding new products based on few examples provided by a specialist	Medium	U1St_R2
U1HR_R3.1.2	The cobot must be able to learn and perform the painting and sanding processes for different shapes, group of colors, and wood types	Medium	U1St_R3
U1HR_R3.1.3	Robot programming by example must be intuitive, the operator must be able to program the robot performing the operation (painting or sanding) on a sample product (either physical or virtual)	Medium	U1St_R4

U1HR_R3.1.4	The cobot must work under human supervision, the operator needs to confirm the actions to be performed by the robot	Medium	U1St_R5
U1HR_R3.1.5	The cobot must be able to paint all pieces of furniture that do not need to be turned vertically and those that, when turned vertically manually by an operator, are fixed to the frame in a stable position	High	U1St_R7
U1HR_R3.1.6	The cobot must stop or adapt the operation speed when operators are within safety distance	High	U1St_R8
U1HR_R3.1.7	The cobot must be able to perceive the properties of the piece of furniture that needs to be painted or sanded (colour and shape)	Medium	U1St_R9
U1HR_R3.1.8	The digitalization system must install ambient data sensors to ensure optimal conditions for painting and worker safety.	Medium	U1St_R11
U1HR_R3.1.9	All solution must comply with the machinery directive and do not harm the operator	High	U1St_R20

U1HR_R3.1.10	The system must comply with Clean Room ISO 8 requirements	Medium	U1St_R21
U1HR_R3.1.11	The robot equipped with low force sensor to prevent harming operators or damaging any physical object	Medium	U1St_R22
U1HR_R3.1.12	The system should be able to manage priority of operations base on operator presence in working areas.	Medium	U1St_R23
U1HR_R3.1.13	The system must be able to rebuild the 3D Space	Medium	U1St_R29
U1HR_R3.1.14	The robot application should meet the normative requirements for collaborative robots according to ISO/TS 15066:2016	High	U1St_R32
U1HR_R3.2	Path Planning		
U1HR_R3.2.1	The cobot must be able to paint pieces of furniture in the three positions of the frame, change from one position to another, and turn the frame in the horizontal axis	High	U1St_R6

5.1.4. System level requirements specification for AI enhancing tools

Table 14. System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
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U1AI_R1	Scene Perception		
U1AI_R1.1	General		
U1AI_R1.1.1	Cobot must learn painting and sanding new products based on few examples provided by a specialist	High	U1St_R2
U1AI_R1.1.2	The cobot must be able to learn and perform the painting and sanding processes for different shapes, group of colors, and wood types	High	U1St_R3
U1AI_R1.1.3	The cobot must work under human supervision, the operator needs to confirm the actions to be performed by the robot	Medium	U1St_R5
U1AI_R1.1.4	The cobot must be able to paint pieces of furniture in the three positions of the frame, change from one position to another, and turn the frame in the horizontal axis	High	U1St_R6
U1AI_R1.1.5	The cobot must be able to paint all pieces of furniture that do not need to be turned vertically and those that, when turned vertically manually by an operator, are fixed to the frame in a stable position		U1St_R7
U1AI_R1.1.6	The cobot must be able to perceive the properties of the piece of furniture that needs to be painted or sanded (colour and shape)		U1St_R9
UxAI_R1.2	Object Detection		
U1AI_R1.2.1	The cobot must stop or adapt the operation speed when operators are within safety distance		U1St_R8
U1AI_R1.2.1	The system must use intuitive visual and/or audible interfaces to alert and communicate with operators		U1St_R10

U1AI_R2	High Level Decision Maker		
U1AI_R2.1	General		
U1AI_R2.1.1	The system must get the information it requires (eg. product identifiers, product colour, shape, material) from corporate software (Finiture or SAP)	High	U1St_R1

5.1.5. System level requirements specification for Social Collaboration

Table 15. System-level requirements specification for social collaboration

ID	Requirement Source	Priority	Requirement
U1SC_R1	Robot transparency U1St_R5	high	Robot has to communicate its impending activities (kinetics, start / end actions, input requirements, error / disturbance alerts, etc.
U1SC_R2	Error analysis U1St_R5		Robot must indicate where errors occur but operator must remain responsible for analysis of criticality and final decisions
U1SC_R3	Robot motion and speed U1St_R8	High	Robot movements should be as smooth as possible and approach the user / shared task at an optimal speed for maintaining human trust
U1SC_R4	Function allocation U1St_R2 & U1St_R2	high	The robot should be allocated monotonous activities to reduce operators' physical strain; operators should retain craft-based tasks and allocated supervision activities.
U1SC_R5	Human supervision U1St_R5	low	Operators must be able to input specific instructions or override/correct robot motion/behaviour.
U1SC_R6	Teaching by demonstration U1St_R4	high	Interface design must be user-centred and enhance usability to enable users to teach by demonstration

5.2. Use Case 2: Reduction of environmental pollution with waste from production of semiconductors

5.2.1. Stakeholder Requirements

Table 16. Stakeholder requirements

ID	Category	Priority	Criterion	Specification
	(Choose one) Constraint/ Functional	(Choose one) Must have/ Should/ Could/ Would	(Choose one) Operational/ Mobility/ HRC/ Perception/ Safety/ Manipulability/ Others (please specify)	Mention the specification
U2St_R1	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must get the information it requires (eg. chip type) and display it in UI
U2St_R2	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must automatically recognize middle of the chip using AI
U2St_R3	Functional	Would	Manipulability	The system would have robotic arm to pick and place chip on the table
U2St_R4	Functional	Should	Manipulability	The gripper should be safe for semiconductors.
U2St_R5	Functional	Should	Perception	The robot equipped with low force sensor to prevent crumpling/crashing chips
U2St_R6	Functional	Would	Perception	The robotic arm equipped with RGBD to locate chips before process
U2St_R7	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must have full traceability of product, LOT ID reading, etc.
U2St_R8	Functional	Should	Operational	Communication with MES, operational time, parameters, LOT ID, other parameters to be saved in MES
U2St_R9	Constraint	Must	Safety	All solution must comply with the machinery directive and do not harm the operator
U2St_R10	Constraint	Must	Other	The system must comply with Clean Room ISO 8 requirements
U2St_R11	Functional	Would	Operational	The system would have a measurement station for machined chips to measure centricity and height after machining process.
U2St_R12	Functional	Would	Perception	The measurement station could measure height by vision or by contact sensor

U2St_R13	Functional	Should	Operational	The system should be able to manage priority of operations base on operator presence in working areas.
U2St_R14	Functional	Would	Operational	The system would have station for inverting chip - 90 or 180 degree when the active surface of chip hidden in the box
U2St_R15	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must use intuitive visual and/or acoustic interfaces to alert and communicate with operators
U2St_R16	Functional	Must	Perception	The digitalization system must install ambient data sensors to ensure optimal conditions for worker safety.
U2St_R17	Functional	Must	Perception	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different cameras to recreate the 3D space
U2St_R18	Functional	Must	Perception	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different sensor to measure the working environment
U2St_R19	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must include an interface to allow the user to deploy the convenient container into the desired device
U2St_R20	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must include an interface to allow the user to monitor the state of the network between the different devices
U2St_R21	Functional	Must	Operational	The cobot must only start if alerts generated have been attended to or closed previously
U2St_R22	Functional	Must	Operational	User interfaces must be responsive and adapt to different end user devices
U2St_R23	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be compatible with the specified robots
U2St_R24	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to configure and verify the connection to other corporate software (SAP or Finiture)

U2St_R25	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to select which product references will be integrated, out of all the existing references in the corporate software (SAP or Finiture)
U2St_R26	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be able to model and store the sequence of movements performed by the operator during cobot training
U2St_R27	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be able to execute the sequence of required actions in order to fulfill a particular task performed by a consequent sequence of movements, recorder from a human operator during the training stages
U2St_R28	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide an interface to start and stop a new training sample for a piece of furniture (shape, colour group, and wood type)
U2St_R29	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide interfaces to validate the results of the training, providing feedback on the performance of the operation learned (e.g. cycle time, materials used, compared to actual baselines)
U2St_R30	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the evolution of performance KPIs
U2St_R31	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to monitor performance indicators for the current production order (e.g. mean cycle time, cycle time histogram, paint used, OEE)
U2St_R32	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be able to rebuild the 3D Space
U2St_R33	Normative	Must Have/Could Have we should not go to deep here	Safety	The robot application should meet the normative requirements for collaborative robots according to ISO/TS 15066:2016

5.2.2. System level requirements specification for hardware

Table 17. System-level requirements specification for hardware

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U2H_R1	Robot System General		
U2H_R1.1	Operating environment and design		
U2H_R1.1.1	The system shall work in the environmental temperatures between 20 and 30 deg C	Medium	U2St_R6
U2H_R1.1.1	Work in a cleanroom	High	U2St_R6
U2H_R2	Manipulator (precision table)		
U2H_R2.1	General		
U2H_R2.1.1	Allow XY positioning in cooperation with microscope	High	U2St_R2
U2H_R2.1.2	Holds one or more chips on the table	High	U2St_R9, U2St_R2
U2H_R2.2	Controller		
U2H_R2.2.1	USB or ETH interface	High	U2St_R4
U2H_R2.2.2	Compatible with precision table	High	U2St_R4, U2St_R9
U2H_R2.2.3	Driven from PC computer	High	U2St_R1
U2H_R2.3	Motorized precision table		
U2H_R2.3.1	XY movement	High	U2St_R2, U2St_R7, U2St_R8, U2St_R9
U2H_R2.3.2	Bidirectional Repeatability <1um	High	U2St_R9

U2H_R2.3.3	Min Repeatable Incremental Movement <1um	High	U2St_R9
U2H_R3	Network Infrastructure		
U2H_R3.1	Station shall be equipped with Ethernet switch for min. 1 port	High	U2St_R4
U2H_R3.2	Station shall be equipped with Ethernet switch for min. 4 ports	Low	U2St_R4
U2H_R3.3	The physical layer should have a bandwidth of 1Gbit/s	High	U2St_R4
U2HR4	Perception Sensors		
U2H_R4.1	Microscope with camera	High	U2St_R2
U2H_R4.2	Microscope field of view from 1x1mm to 3x3mm	High	U2St_R2
U2H_R4.3	Microscope resolution 1px/1um	High	U2St_R2

5.2.3. System level requirements specification for Human-Robot Collaboration

Table 18. System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
E.g. UxHR_R1	Specify requirement	High/Medium/Low	Refer to ID of stake holder requirement Table 6 (or) specify as derived
U2HR_R1	Human Robot Interactive Interfaces		
U2HR_R1.1	General		
U2HR_R.1.1.1	The system must get the information it requires (eg. chip type) and display it in UI	Low	U2St_R1
U2HR_R.1.1.2	User interfaces must provide visual alerts to warn users of errors	Medium	U2St_R15
U2HR_R.1.1.3	The cobot must only start if alerts generated have been attended to or closed previously	High	U2St_R21

U2HR_R.1.1.4	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different cameras to recreate the 3D space	Medium	U2St_R17
U2HR_R.1.1.5	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different sensor to measure the working environment	Medium	U2St_R18
U2HR_R.1.1.6	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the current status of the cobot (eg. whether it is operating or not, what is the current production order, what is the status of the process)	Medium	U2St_R1,U2St_R7,U2St_R8
U2HR_R.1.1.7	The system must include an interface to allow the user to deploy the convenient container into the desired device	Medium	U2St_R19
U2HR_R.1.1.8	User interfaces must be responsive and adapt to different end user devices	Medium	U2St_R22
U2HR_R.1.1.9	ROS node via Ethernet	Medium	
U2HR_R.1.1.10	XY positioning Ethernet interface	High	
U2HR_R.1.1.11	Camera interface Ethernet (or USB)	High	
U2HR_R1.2	Configuration Interface		
U2HR_R.1.2.1	The system must provide user interfaces to configure and verify the connection to other corporate software (SAP or Finiture)	Low	U2St_R24

U2HR_R.1.2.2	The system must provide user interfaces to select which product references will be integrated, out of all the existing references in the corporate software (SAP or Finiture)	Medium	U2St_R25
U2HR_R1.3	Training		
U2HR_R.1.3.1	The system must be able to model and store the sequence of movements performed by the operator during cobot training	High	U2St_R26
U2HR_R.1.3.2	The system must provide an interface to start and stop a new training sample for a piece of furniture (shape, colour group, and wood type)	Medium	U2St_R28
U2HR_R.1.3.3	The system must provide interfaces to validate the results of the training, providing feedback on the performance of the operation learned (e.g. cycle time, materials used, compared to actual baselines)	Low	U2St_R29
U2HR_R1.4	Operations Control		
U2HR_R.1.4.1	The system must provide user interfaces to confirm the current production order and product information (chip type). If the operator does not confirm the robot will not perform any operation.	Medium	U2St_R7,U2St_R8

U2HR_R.1.4.2	The system must alert the operator if there is an error during an operation	Medium	U2St_R15
U2HR_R.1.4.3	The system must alert the operator when it has finalised an operation step that requires manual intervention	Medium	U2St_R15
U2HR_R1.5	Performance Monitoring		
U2HR_R.1.5.1	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the evolution of performance KPIs	Low	U2St_R30
U2HR_R.1.5.2	The system must provide user interfaces to monitor performance indicators for the current production order (e.g. mean cycle time, cycle time histogram, paint used, OEE)	Low	U2St_R31
U2HR_R.1.5.3	The system must include an interface to allow the user to monitor the state of the network between the different devices	Low	U2St_R20
U2HR_R2	Safety		
U2HR_2.1	General		
U2HR_R2.1.1	Must be safe for human	High	U2St_R9, U2St_R16
U2HR_R3	Robot Manipulation		
U2HR_R3.1	General		
U2HR_R3.1.1	Precision table act as robot	High	U2St_R23, U2St_R27
U2HR_R3.1.2	The system must automatically recognize middle of the chip using AI	High	U2St_R2,

U2HR_R3.1.3	Assisting a human in positioning the chip	High	U2St_R3
U2HR_R3.1.4	Assisting a human in glueing a stick	Low	U2St_R27
U2HR_R3.1.5	The digitalization system must install ambient data sensors to ensure optimal conditions for worker safety.	Medium	U2St_R32
U2HR_R3.1.6	Chips are placed manually by human on the precision table	Medium	U2St_R16
U2HR_R3.1.7	Manual movement of the stick by human	High	U2St_R27
U2HR_R3.1.8	Automatic movement of the stick if possible	Low	U2St_R27
U2HR_R3.1.9	Applying glue to a stick manually by human	High	U2St_R27
U2HR_R3.1.10	The gripper should be safe for semiconductors.	High	U2St_R4
U2HR_R3.1.11	The robotic arm equipped with low force sensor to prevent crumpling/crashing chips	Medium	U2St_R5
U2HR_R3.1.12	The robotic arm equipped with RGBD to locate chips before process	High	U2St_R6
U2HR_R3.1.13	All solution must comply with the machinery directive and do not harm the operator	High	U2St_R9
U2HR_R3.1.14	The system must comply with Clean Room ISO 8 requirements	High	U2St_R10

U2HR_R3.1.15	The system would have a measurement station for machined chips to measure centricity and height after machining process.	Low	U2St_R11
U2HR_R3.1.16	The measurement station could measure height by vision or by contact sensor	Medium	U2St_R12
U2HR_R3.1.17	The system should be able to manage priority of operations base on operator presence in working areas.	Medium	U2St_R13
U2HR_R3.1.18	The system would have station for inverting chip - 90 or 180 degree when the active surface of chip hidden in the box	Medium	U2St_R14
U2HR_R3.1.19	The digitalization system must install ambient data sensors to ensure optimal conditions for worker safety.		U2St_R16
U2HR_R3.1.20	The system must be able to rebuild the 3D Space	High	U2St_R32
U2HR_R3.1.21	The robot application should meet the normative requirements for collaborative robots according to ISO/TS 15066:2016	High	U2St_R33
U2HR_R3.2	Path Planning		
U2HR_R3.2.1	Driven automatically to set demanded position	Medium	U2St_R27

5.2.4. System level requirements specification for AI enhancing tools

Table 19. System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U2AI_R1	Scene Perception		
U2AI_R1.1	General		
U2AI_R1.1.1	Recognition of the chip matrix (if applied)	Medium	U2St_R2
U2AI_R1.1.1	Learning by demonstration	High	U2St_R2
U2AI_R1.2	Object Detection		
U2AI_R1.2.1	Recognition of the specific shape in the middle of the chip	High	U2St_R2
U2AI_R1.2.1	Recognition of the random shape in the middle of the chip	Medium	U2St_R2
U2AI_R1.2.1	Learning of recognition shape of the middle of the chip by demonstration	High	U2St_R2
U2AI_R2	High Level Decision Maker		
U2AI_R2.1	General		
U2AI_R2.1.1	Automatic precision table adjustment basing on recognized middle of the chip	High	U2St_R2, U2St_R9
U2AI_R2.1.2	Automatic decision if middle of the chip found	High	U2St_R2

5.2.5. System level requirements specification for Social Collaboration

Table 20. System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U2SC_R1	Automatic chip positioning	high	Workload reduction - reduce time operator focuses on screen

U2SC_R2	Automatic precision table control	high	Workload reduction – less screw rotating by fingers
U2SC_R3	Design the assembly station with precision table and microscope	medium	Better ergonomic design of workspace
U2SC_R4	Error analysis	low	Robot should indicate where errors occur but operators should retain responsibility for quality control checks, analysis of criticality and final decisions.

5.3. Use Case 3: Brewery/Food industry transformation towards Industry 5.0

5.3.1. Stakeholder Requirements

Table 21. Stakeholder requirements

ID	Category	Priority	Criterion	Specification
U3St_R1	Functional	Must	Operational	The cobot must lift sacks of powder from a pallet and place them upon the conveyor for further processing
U3St_R2	Functional	Must	Operational	The cobot must choose sacks from different pallets
U3St_R3	Functional	Must	Manipulability	The cobot must lift bottles
U3St_R4	Functional	Must	Perception	The system must identify the brand of the returnable bottle
U3St_R5	Functional	Must	Operational	The cobot must put the identified bottle to the corresponding place
U3St_R6	Functional	Must	Operational	The cobot must follow the worker when collaborating for creating custom orders

U3St_R7	Functional	Must	HRC	The cobot must assist the worker by transporting products
U3St_R8	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must include sensors to prevent harm or damage
U3St_R9	Functional	Must	Perception	The system must have visual and/or auditory alerts
U3St_R10	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must only initiate if all alerts generated have been attended to

5.3.2. System level requirements specification for hardware

Table 22. System-level requirements specification for hardware

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U3H_R1	Robot System General		
U3H_R1.1	Operating environment and design		
U3H_R1.1.1	The systems shall work in the environmental temperatures between +20 and +35 deg C	High	Derived
U3H_R2	Robots		
U3H_R2.1	General		
U3H_R2.1.1	6-axis collaborative robot arms	High	U3St_R1, U3St_R3, U3St_R5
U3H_R2.1.2	Autonomous Mobile Robot	High	U3St_R6
U3H_R2.1.3	Robot Lift	High	U3St_R1
UxH_R2.2	Gripper		
U3H_R2.2.1	Capable of holding a beer bottle	High	U3St_R3
U3H_R3	Network Infrastructure		
U3H_R3.1	Each stationary system shall be equipped with an Ethernet switch	High	Derived
U3H_R3.2	The physical layer should have a bandwidth of at least 1GB	High	Derived
U3H_R3.3	Router	High	Derived
U3HR4	Perception Sensors		
U3H_R4.1	5 RGBD Cameras	High	Derived, U3St_R2, U3St_R4

5.3.3. System level requirements specification for Human-Robot Collaboration

Table 23 System-level requirements specification for human robot collaboration

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U3HR_R1	Robot Manipulation		
U3HR_R1.1	Path Planning		
U3HR_R1.1.1	The cobot must be able to transport products from pallet to pallet	High	U3St_R7

5.3.4. System level requirements specification for AI enhancing tools

Table 24. System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U3AI_R1	Scene Perception		
U3AI_R1.1	General		
U3AI_R1.1.1	The cobot must always be aware of its surroundings when traversing the storage area	High	U3St_R6, U3St_R7
U3AI_R1.2	Object Detection		
U3AI_R1.2.1	The system must identify the brand of the bottle by its different shape, colour or sticker	High	U3St_R4

5.3.5. System level requirements specification for Social Collaboration

Social Collaboration (corresponding to WP5 solutions).

Table 25. System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U3SC_R1	Removal of parts of the process where humans are either: (A)	High	Physical Discomfort, U3St_R1, U3St_R7

	<p>experiencing high physical strain - lifting full crates of bottles, bags of powder (22.7 kg), (B) experiencing physical discomfort - lifting bottles which might have remaining water in them, (C) there is potential of injury - bottles breaking, glass cutting hands, (D) being exposed to dangerous materials - needing to handle bags of powder with potential harmful impact on their long term health.</p>		
U3SC_R2	<p>Reduction of handling materials by hand which are not dry and spilling water on themselves. Reduction of instances where the user is dealing with the materials which could have potential impact on their health.</p>	High	Safety, U3St_R1, U3St_R3, U3St_R5
U3SC_R3	<p>Operators should retain responsibility for error and quality checks, analysis of criticality and final decisions.</p>	High	Self-Efficacy, U3St_R7

5.4. Use Case 4: Adaptable & Collaborative Workstation

5.4.1. Stakeholder Requirements

Table 26. Stakeholder requirements

ID	Category	Priority	Criterion	Specification
U4St_R1	Functional	Must	Perception	The system shall inspect the hoods to detect defects while the cover of the product is open.

U4St_R2	Functional	Must	Operational	The system shall pack the cable.
U4St_R3	Functional	Must	Operational	The system shall stick the packed cable.
U4St_R4	Functional	Must	Operational	The system shall conduct tests.
U4St_R4.1	Functional	Must	Operational	The system shall conduct grounding tests while the cover of the product is open.
U4St_R4.2	Functional	Must	Operational	The system shall conduct functional tests while the cover of the product is open.
U4St_R5	Functional	Must	Operational	The system shall place the metal label inside the product.
U4St_R6	Functional	Must	HRC	The system shall filter assembling. and the cobot shall to assist the operator by doing the manipulation of hood body.
U4St_R7	Functional	Must	Mobility	The system shall bag the product process.
U4St_R8	Functional	Must	Mobility	The system shall put barcode labels and documents near the product.
U4St_R9	Constraint	Must	Perception	The inspection of the product shall take at most 12 seconds.
U4St_R10	Constraint	Must	Perception	Making inspection is according to technical specifications
U4St_R11	Constraint	Must	Operational	The grounding test of the product shall take at most 13 seconds.
U4St_R12	Constraint	Must	Operational	The grounding test is ok/ ko
U4St_R13	Constraint	Must	Operational	The functional test of the product shall take at most 17 seconds.
U4St_R14	Constraint	Must	Operational	ok/ ko lighting lamp
U4St_R15	Constraint	Must	Perception	ok/ko engine functional levels
U4St_R16	Constraint	Must	Perception	ok/ko perception of button
U4St_R17	Constraint	Must	Operational	ok/ko exhausting level of product (hood)
U4St_R18	Constraint	Could	Operational	The packing time is at 5 seconds
U4St_R19	Constraint	Could	Operational	Sticking of packed cable is at 7 seconds
U4St_R20	Constraint	Could	Operational	Placing the metal label inside the product is at 7 seconds
U4St_R21	Constraint	Must	HRC	Assembling filter is at 6 seconds.
U4St_R22	Constraint	Could	Mobility	Bagging the product is at 11 seconds
U4St_R23	Constraint	Must	Mobility	Putting the barcode labels and documents near the product are at 4 seconds

U4St_R24	Functional	Would	assessment	The system shall estimate human status
U4St_R25	Functional	Must	Operational	The robot shall work into the closed working environment
U4St_R26	Functional	Must	Operational	The robot shall work with human operators in the same working environment
U4St_R27	Functional	Must	Operational	The robot application should meet the normative requirements for collaborative robots according to ISO/TS 15066:2016
U4St_R28	Functional	Must	Operational	In order to start the functional test, visual control and information that the hood is in the appropriate position for the test will be taken from the system.
U4St_R29	Functional	Would	Manipulability	The operator has to lift the hood from the conveyor to work station and between two different work stations
U4St_R30	Functional	Must	Operational	The system will perform propeller cracks checking tests.
U4St_R31	Functional	Must	Operational	The test results will be shown to the operator with the help of a screen to be installed in the cab.
U4St_R32	Functional	Must	Perception	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different cameras to recreate the 3D space
U4St_R33	Functional	Should	Operational	The system must have full traceability of product, LOT ID reading, etc.
U4St_R34	Constraint	Must	Safety	Communication with MES, operational time, parameters, LOT ID, other parameters to be saved in MES
U4St_R35	Constraint	Must	Other	All solution must comply with the machinery directive and do not harm the operator
U4St_R36	Functional	Would	Operational	The system must comply with Clean Room ISO 8 requirements
U4St_R37	Functional	Would	Perception	The system must get the information it requires and display it in UI
U4St_R38	Functional	Should	Operational	The robot equipped with low force sensor to prevent harming operators or damaging any physical object

U4St_R39	Functional	Would	Operational	The system should be able to manage priority of operations based on operator presence in working areas.
U4St_R40	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must use intuitive visual and/or accousting interfaces to alert and communicate with operators
U4St_R41	Functional	Must	Perception	The digitalization system must install ambient data sensors to ensure optimal conditions for worker safety.
U4St_R42	Functional	Must	Perception	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different sensor to measure the working environment
U4St_R43	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must include an interface to allow the user to deploy the convenient container into the desired device
U4St_R44	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must include an interface to allow the user to monitor the state of the network between the different devices
U4St_R45	Functional	Must	Operational	The cobot must only start if alerts generated have been attended to or closed previously
U4St_R46	Functional	Must	Operational	User interfaces must be responsive and adapt to different end user devices
U4St_R47	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be compatible with the specified robots
U4St_R48	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be able to model and store the sequence of movements performed by the operator during cobot training
U4St_R49	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be able to execute the sequence of required actions in order to fulfill a particular task performed by a consequent sequence of movements, recorder from a human operator during the training stages
U4St_R50	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide an interface to start and stop a new training sample
U4St_R51	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide interfaces to validate the results of the training, providing feedback on the performance of the operation learned

				(e.g. cycle time, materials used, compared to actual baselines)
U4St_R52	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the evolution of performance KPIs
U4St_R53	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to monitor performance indicators for the current production order (e.g. mean cycle time, cycle time histogram, paint used, OEE)
U4St_R54	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be able to rebuild the 3D Space
U4St_R55	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to configure and verify the connection to other corporate software (SAP or Finiture)
U4St_R56	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to select which product references will be integrated, out of all the existing references in the corporate software (SAP or Finiture)

5.4.2. System level requirements specification for hardware

Table 27. System-level requirements specification for hardware

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U4H_R1	Robot System General		
U4H_R1.1	Operating environment and design		
U4H_R1.1.1	The cobot must work into the closed working environment	High	U4St_R25
U4H_R1.1.2	There will be two workstations for functional tests and visual inspection. The hood received by the Operator from the belt will be transported to the workstation.	High	U4St_R26
U4H_R1.1.3	Once the hood is placed on the workstation, the cobot will begin the tests.	High	U4St_R1, U4St_R4.1, U4St_R4.2, U4St_R26
U4H_R2	Manipulator		

U4H_R2.1	Controller	High	
U4H_R2.1.1	Cobots have its own controllers.	High	U4St_R49
U4H_R2.1.2	Cobots controllers communicate with SPS test device via ethernet.	High	U4St_R4
U4H_R2.1.3	Communication will be established between the cobot and the camera via ethernet	High	U4St_R1
U4H_R2.1.4	Communication will be established between the cobot and the microphone via ethernet.	High	U4St_R28
U4H_R2.2	Gripper		
U4H_R2.2.1	The gripper on the cobot which perform visual detection should hold camera and illumination system.	High	U4St_R1
U4H_R2.2.2	The gripper on the cobot which perform functional test and grounding test have two types of gripper. One for grounding test and one for touch the screen.	High	U4St_R4.1 U4St_R4.2
U4H_R2.2.3	The gripper for functional tests should interact with touch screen.	Medium	U4St_R13
U4H_R2.2.4	The gripper must be able to turn on and turn off screen.	High	U4St_R13
U4H_R2.2.5	The gripper for grounding test should be conductive.	High	U4St_R4.1
U4H_R3	Network Infrastructure		
U4H_R3.1	The robot shall be equipped with Ethernet switch for min. 2 ports	H	Derived
U4H_R3.2	The physical layer should have a bandwidth of 100Mbps	H	Derived
U4H_R3.3	The robot should be equipped with a router with GSM module	H	Derived
U4HR4	Perception Sensors		
U4H_R4.1	The system shall utilize industrial optic camera data of the product's surface in order to inspect defects in at most 12 seconds and in compliance to technical specifications.	High	U4St_R1, U4St_R9, U4St_R10

U4H_R4.1.1	The RGBD Camera in the system (static Camera System) shall provide images of the product's surface to the AI service that will perform inspection.	High	U4St_R1, U4St_R10	U4St_R9,
U4H_R4.1.2	The system shall include one or more High Resolution Gray Scale Camera and lens (static Camera System)	High	U4St_R1, U4St_R10	U4St_R9,
U4H_R4.1.3	The system shall include an illumination pane, for controlled illumination.	High	U4St_R1, U4St_R10	U4St_R9,
U4H_R4.1.4	The system may utilize cables to connect camera to the network.	Medium	U4St_R1, U4St_R10	U4St_R9,
U4H_R4.1.5	The system will tell the result of propeller cracks checking test with the help of the data obtained from the microphone.	High	U4St_R28	
U4H_R4.1.6	The system will have a filter to prevent surface reflections/glare in the camera images.	Medium	U4St_R1, U4St_R10	U4St_R9,
U4HR5	Human Monitoring			
U4St_R5.1	The human monitoring system may need two RGB cameras.	Low	U4St_R24	
U4St_R5.2	The human monitoring system may need at least one wearable physiological sensor.	Low	U4St_R24	
U4St_R5.3	The human monitoring system need computing hardware (PC).	Low	U4St_R24	
U4St_R5.4	The human monitoring system needs Human Machine Interface (display).	Low	U4St_R24	

5.4.3. System level requirements specification for Human-Robot Collaboration

Table 28. System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U4HR_R1	Human Robot Interactive Interfaces		
U4HR_R1.1	General		
U4HR_R.1.1.1	The system must have full traceability of product, LOT ID reading, etc.	Medium	U5St_R33

U4HR_R.1.1.2	Communication with MES, operational time, parameters, LOT ID, other parameters to be saved in MES	Medium	U5St_R34
U4HR_R.1.1.3	The system must get the information it requires and display it in UI	Low	U5St_R37
U4HR_R.1.1.4	The system must use intuitive visual and/or accousting interfaces to alert and communicate with operators	Medium	U5St_R40
U4HR_R.1.1.5	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different sensor to measure the working environment	Medium	U5St_R42
U4HR_R.1.1.6	The system must include an interface to allow the user to deploy the convenient container into the desired device	Medium	U5St_R43
U4HR_R.1.1.7	The cobot must only start if alerts generated have been attended to or closed previously	High	U5St_R45
U4HR_R.1.1.8	User interfaces must be responsive and adapt to different end user devices	Medium	U5St_R46
U4HR_R.1.1.9	User interfaces must provide visual alerts to warn users of errors	Medium	U3St_R37, U3St_R40, U3St_R45
U4HR_R.1.1.10	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different cameras to recreate the 3D space	Medium	U5St_R32
U5HR_R.1.1.11	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the current status of the cobot (eg. whether it is operating or not, what is the current production order, what is the status of the process)	Medium	U3St_R37, U3St_R40

U4HR_R.1.1.11	The test results will be shown to the operator with the help of a screen to be installed in the cab.	Medium	U4St_R31
U4HR_R1.2	Configuration Interface		
U4HR_R.1.2.1	The system must provide user interfaces to configure and verify the connection to other corporate software (SAP or Finiture)	Low	U3St_R55
U4HR_R.1.2.2	The system must provide user interfaces to select which product references will be integrated, out of all the existing references in the corporate software (SAP or Finiture)	Medium	U3St_R56
U4HR_R1.3	Training		
U4HR_R.1.3.1	The system must be able to model and store the sequence of movements performed by the operator during cobot training	High	U3St_R48
U4HR_R.1.3.3	The system must provide an interface to start and stop a new training sample	Medium	U3St_R50
U4HR_R.1.3.4	The system must provide interfaces to validate the results of the training, providing feedback on the performance of the operation learned (e.g. cycle time, materials used, compared to actual baselines)	Low	U3St_R51
U4HR_R1.4	Operations Control		
U4HR_R.1.4.1	The system must provide user interfaces to confirm the current production order and product information. If the operator does not confirm the robot will not perform any operation.	Medium	U3St_R37, U3St_R40
U4HR_R.1.4.2	The system must alert the operator if there is an error during an operation	Medium	U3St_R40, U3St_R45

U4HR_R.1.4.3	The system must alert the operator when it has finalised an operation step that requires manual intervention	Medium	U3St_R40, U3St_R45
U4HR_R.1.4.4	The cobot(s) must receive instructions from SAP/invoice on the exact containers of the pallet quantity/SKU when packaging and palletizing of custom orders	Medium	U3St_R37, U3St_R40
U4HR_R1.5	Performance Monitoring		
U4HR_R.1.5.1	The system must include an interface to allow the user to monitor the state of the network between the different devices	Low	U3St_R44
U4HR_R.1.5.2	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the evolution of performance KPIs	Low	U3St_R52
U4HR_R.1.5.3	The system must provide user interfaces to monitor performance indicators for the current production order (e.g. mean cycle time, cycle time histogram, paint used, OEE)	Low	U3St_R53
U4HR_R2	Specify details		
U4HR_2.1	General		
U4HR_R2.1.1	Must be safe for human	High	U3St_R41, U3St_R27
U4HR_R3	Robot Manipulation		
U4HR_R3.1	General		
U4HR_R3.1.1	All solution must comply with the machinery directive and do not harm the operator	High	U3St_R35
U4HR_R3.1.2	The system must comply with Clean Room ISO 8 requirements	High	U3St_R36

U4HR_R3.1.3	The robot equipped with low force sensor to prevent harming operators or damaging any physical object	Medium	U3St_R38
U4HR_R3.1.4	The system should be able to manage priority of operations base on operator presence in working areas.	Medium	U3St_R39
U4HR_R3.1.5	The digitalization system must install ambient data sensors to ensure optimal conditions for worker safety.	High	U3St_R41
U4HR_R3.1.6	The system must be compatible with the specified robots	Medium	U3St_R47
U3HR_R3.1.7	The system must be able to execute the sequence of required actions in order to fulfill a particular task peromed by a consequent sequence of movements, recorder from a human operator during the training stages	Medium	U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.7	The system must be able to rebuild the 3D Space	High	U3St_R54
U4HR_R3.1.8	The robot application should meet the normative requirements for collaborative robots according to ISO/TS 15066:2016	High	U3St_R57
U4HR_R3.1.9	The system shall inspect the hoods to detect defects while the cover of the product is open.	Medium	U4St_R1, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.10	The system shall pack the cable.	Medium	U4St_R2, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.11	The system shall stick the packed cable.	Medium	U4St_R3, U3St_R49

U4HR_R3.1.12	The system shall conduct tests.	Medium	U4St_R4, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.13	The system shall conduct grounding tests while the cover of the product is open.	Medium	U4St_R4.1, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.14	The system shall conduct functional tests while the cover of the product is open.	Medium	U4St_R4.2, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.15	The system shall place the metal label inside the product.	Medium	U4St_R5, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.16	The system shall filter assembling. and the cobot shall to assist the operator by doing the manipulation of hood body.	Medium	U4St_R6, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.17	The system shall bag the product process.	Medium	U4St_R7, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.18	The system shall put barcode labels and documents near the product.	Medium	U4St_R8, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.19	The inspection of the product shall take at most 12 seconds.	Medium	U4St_R9, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.20	Making inspection is according to technical specifications	Medium	U4St_R10, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.21	The grounding test of the product shall take at most 13 seconds.	Medium	U4St_R11, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.22	The grounding test is ok/ ko	Medium	U4St_R12, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.23	The functional test of the product shall take at most 17 seconds.	Medium	U4St_R13, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.24	ok/ ko lighting lamp	Medium	U4St_R14, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.25	ok/ko engine functional levels	Medium	U4St_R15, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.26	ok/ko perception of button	Medium	U4St_R16, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.27	ok/ko exhausting level of product (hood)	Medium	U4St_R17, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.28	The packing time is at 5 seconds	Medium	U4St_R18, U3St_R49

U4HR_R3.1.29	Sticking of packed cable is at 7 seconds	Medium	U4St_R19, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.30	Placing the metal label inside the product is at 7 seconds	Medium	U4St_R20, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.31	Assembling filter is at 6 seconds.	Medium	U4St_R21, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.32	Bagging the product is at 11 seconds	Medium	U4St_R22, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.33	Putting the barcode labels and documents near the product are at 4 seconds	Medium	U4St_R23, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.34	The system shall estimate human status	Medium	U4St_R24, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.35	The robot shall work into the closed working environment	Medium	U4St_R25, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.36	The robot shall work with human operators in the same working environment	Medium	U4St_R26, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.37	In order to start the functional test, visual control and information that the hood is in the appropriate position for the test will be taken from the system.	Medium	U4St_R28, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.38	The operator has to lift the hood from the conveyor to work station and between two different work stations	Medium	U4St_R29, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.1.39	The system will perform propeller cracks checking tests.	Medium	U4St_R30, U3St_R49
U4HR_R3.2	Path Planning		
U4HR_R3.2.1	Driven automatically to set demanded position	Medium	U3St_R49

5.4.4. System level requirements specification for AI enhancing tools

Table 29. System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U4AI_R1	Scene Perception		
U4AI_R1.1	General		
U4AI_R1.1	The cobot(s) must always be aware of their surroundings when passing through the working area	High	U4St_R24
U4AI_R1.2	Inspection functionalities based on vision to determine the defect in proper position	High	U4St_R24, U4St_R1
U4AI_R1.3	The camera should detect the product from its environment and check whether product is placed on the workstations	High	U4St_R4 U4St_R1
U4AI_R1.2	Object Detection		
U4AI_R1.2.1	The cobot shall learn to detect defects.	High	U4St_R1, U4St_R9, U4St_R10, U4H_R4.1
U4AI_R1.2.2	The AI shall utilize camera data.	High	U4St_R1, U4St_R9, U4St_R10, U4H_R4.1.1
U4AI_R1.2.3	The camera and AI system shall detect the product.	High	U4St_R4 U4St_R1
U4AI_R1.2.4	The camera and AI system shall track the product while carrying by human operator to the workstations	High	U4St_R4 U4St_R1
U4AI_R1.2.5	The camera and artificial intelligence system will check for the presence of missing components on the hood.	High	U4St_R4, U4St_R1
U4AI_R1.3	Defect Detection		
U4AI_R1.3.1	The camera and artificial intelligence system will detect defects on the hood glass surface and inform the operator.	High	U4St_R4, U4St_R1

U4AI_R1.3.2	The camera and artificial intelligence system will detect defects in the hood metal surface and inform the operator.	High	U4St_R4, U4St_R1
U4AI_R2	Human Monitoring		
U4AI_R2.1	The system should be able to acquire the worker's face images by the camera.	Low	U4St_R24
U4AI_R2.1	The system should be able to acquire a full-body images of the back of the worker by the camera.	Low	U4St_R24

5.4.5. System level requirements specification for Social Collaboration

Table 30. System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U4SC_R1	Human Monitoring		
U4SC_R1.1	The system should be able to infer joint points from full-body images of the worker captured by the camera.	Low	U4St_R24
U4SC_R1.2	The system should be able to acquire the worker's physiological information.	Low	U4St_R24
U4SC_R2	Warning Systems		
U4SC_R2.1	Human Warning System		
U4SC_R2.1	When the robots working on the workstations encounter any errors, they will be alerted with the help of the screen and buzzer system located in the field.	High	U4St_R29

5.5. Use Case 5 : Generic Demonstrator AI-Control for Natural, Multi-modal Collaboration

5.5.1. Stakeholder Requirements

Table 31. Stakeholder requirements

ID	Category	Priority	Criterion	Specification
U5St_R1	Functional	Must	Grasping	Stable grasping of PCBs
U5St_R2	Functional	Must	Interface	Interface for Non-expert to configure a grasping process to the robot
U5St_R3	Functional	Must	Manipulation/ Perception	Manipulation correction of the grasped PCB so that the next step in the process can be achieved
U5St_R4	Functional	Must	Manipulation/ Perception	Efficient non-overlapping PCB placement (bin-packing)
U5St_R5	Functional	Must	Manipulation / Perception	Deposit the PCB into the testing adapter for testing the PCB
U5St_R6	Functional	Must	Interface	Configuration of the process flow using interactive and natural interfaces
U5St_R7	Functional	Must	Operational	Recovery strategies if one the robot process fails or is not achieved
U5St_R8	Functional	Could	Manipulation	The robot system, what is responsible for the PBC handling can be easily applied on similar locally separated Workplaces.
U5St_R9	Constraint	Must	Operational	The PCB size (maximum allowable) should allow manipulation with one flow gripper
U5St_R10	Constraint	Must	Operational	The temperature in the use case facility should be constant (+- 2C)
U5St_R11	Functional	Must	Perception	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different cameras to recreate the 3D space
U5St_R12	Functional	Should	Operational	The system must have full traceability of product, LOT ID reading, etc.
U5St_R13	Constraint	Must	Safety	Communication with MES, operational time, parameters, LOT ID, other parameters to be saved in MES
U5St_R14	Constraint	Must	Other	All solution must comply with the machinery directive and do not harm the operator

U5St_R15	Functional	Would	Operational	The system must comply with Clean Room ISO 8 requirements
U5St_R16	Functional	Would	Perception	The system must get the information it requires and display it in UI
U5St_R17	Functional	Should	Operational	The robot equipped with low force sensor to prevent harming operators or damaging any physical object
U5St_R18	Functional	Would	Operational	The system should be able to manage priority of operations base on operator presence in working areas.
U5St_R19	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must use intuitive visual and/or voice interfaces to alert and communicate with operators
U5St_R20	Functional	Must	Perception	The digitalization system must install ambient data sensors to ensure optimal conditions for worker safety.
U5St_R21	Functional	Must	Perception	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different sensor to measure the working environment
U5St_R22	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must include an interface to allow the user to deploy the convenient container into the desired device
U5St_R23	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must include an interface to allow the user to monitor the state of the network between the different devices
U5St_R24	Functional	Must	Operational	The cobot must only start if alerts generated have been attended to or closed previously
U5St_R25	Functional	Must	Operational	User interfaces must be responsive and adapt to different end user devices
U5St_R26	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be compatible with the specified robots
U5St_R27	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be able to model and store the sequence of movements performed by the operator during cobot training
U5St_R28	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be able to execute the sequence of required actions in order to fulfill a particular task performed by a consequent sequence of movements, recorder from a human operator during the training stages

U5St_R29	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide an interface to start and stop a new training sample
U5St_R30	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide interfaces to validate the results of the training, providing feedback on the performance of the operation learned (e.g. cycle time, materials used, compared to actual baselines)
U5St_R31	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the evolution of performance KPIs
U5St_R32	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to monitor performance indicators for the current production order (e.g. mean cycle time, cycle time histogram, paint used, OEE)
U5St_R33	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must be able to rebuild the 3D Space
U5St_R34	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to configure and verify the connection to other corporate software (SAP or Finiture)
U5St_R35	Functional	Must	Operational	The system must provide user interfaces to select which product references will be integrated, out of all the existing references in the corporate software (SAP or Finiture)
U5St_R36	Normative	Must	Safety	The robot application should meet the normative requirements for collaborative robots according to ISO/TS 15066:2016

5.5.2. System level requirements specification for hardware

Table 32. System-level requirements specification for hardware

ID	Requirement Source	Priority	Requirement
U5H_R1	Robot System General		
U5H_R1.1	Operating environment and design		
U5H_R1.1.1	derived	High	The system shall work in the environmental temperatures between 20 and +35 deg C

U5H_R2	Manipulator			
U5H_R2.1	General			
U5H_R2.1.1	derived	High	6-axis collaborative manipulator robots with a minimum payload of 5 kg and a minimum reach of 1300 mm. For PCB manipulation.	
U5H_R2.1.2	U5St_R9	Medium	Autonomous Mobile Robot (AMRs).	
U5H_R2.3	Gripper			
U5H_R2.3.1	U5St_R11	High	A gripper capable of holding printed circuit boards (PCBs) of various sizes and weights, whether or not they have components attached to them.	
U5H_R3	Network Infrastructure			
U5H_R3.1	derived	High	The cobot shall be equipped with at least 1 communication port. (Ethernet, wifi)	
U5H_R3.2	derived	High	The physical layer should have a bandwidth of 1 GB for wired network.	
U5H_R3.2	derived	High	Router/Switch	
U4HR4	Perception Sensors			
U4H_R4.1	U5St_R1, U5St_R3, U5St_R6	U5St_R2, U5St_R4,	High	RGBD Camera on end effector, for Human centered teach-in-process and grasping process.
U4H_R4.2	U5St_R6		High	A grayscale camera with a high resolution and a suitable lens for pose correction system.
U4H_R4.2	U5St_R6		High	RGBD Camera for pose correction system.
U4H_R4.3	U5St_R6		High	Illumination panel for pose correction system.
U4H_R4.4	U5St_R7		High	Force Torque Sensor that can be attached to the flange of the robot.

U4H_R4.5	U5St_R8	High	A Microphone array for neural language module.
U4H_R4.6	derived	High	A visual sensor system designed for detecting human poses within the work area.
U4H_R4.7	derived	Medium	A DMC reader.
U4H_R5	Infrastructure		
U4H_R5.1	U5St_R8	High	Consumer Tablet
U4H_R5.2	derived	High	Multiple digital and analog I/O channels
U4H_R5.3	U5St_R5	High	Industrial vacuum
U4H_R5.4	derived	High	Edge device / Edge AI
U4H_R5.5	U5St_R8	High	Training platform

5.5.3. System level requirements specification for Human-Robot Collaboration

Table 33 System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement	Priority	Requirement Source
U5HR_R1	Human Robot Interactive Interfaces		
U5HR_R1.1	General		
U5HR_R.1.1.1	The system must have full traceability of product, LOT ID reading, etc.	Medium	U5St_R12
U5HR_R.1.1.2	Communication with MES, operational time, parameters, LOT ID, other parameters to be saved in MES	Medium	U5St_R13
U5HR_R.1.1.3	The system must get the information it requires and display it in UI	Low	U5St_R16
U5HR_R.1.1.4	The system must use intuitive visual and/or accousting interfaces to alert and communicate with operators	Medium	U5St_R19

U5HR_R.1.1.5	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different sensor to measure the working environment	Medium	U5St_R21
U5HR_R.1.1.6	The system must include an interface to allow the user to deploy the convenient container into the desired device	Medium	U5St_R22
U5HR_R.1.1.7	The cobot must only start if alerts generated have been attended to or closed previously	High	U5St_R24
U5HR_R.1.1.8	User interfaces must be responsive and adapt to different end user devices	Medium	U5St_R25
U5HR_R.1.1.9	User interfaces must provide visual alerts to warn users of errors	Medium	U3St_R16, U3St_R19, U3St_R24
U5HR_R.1.1.10	The system must include an interface to allow the user to calibrate the different cameras to recreate the 3D space	Medium	U5St_R11
U5HR_R.1.1.11	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the current status of the cobot (eg. whether it is operating or not, what is the current production order, what is the status of the process)	Medium	U5St_R16, U5St_R19
U5HR_R1.2	Configuration Interface		
U5HR_R.1.2.1	The system must provide user interfaces to configure and verify the connection to other corporate software (SAP or Finiture)	Low	U5St_R34
U5HR_R.1.2.2	The system must provide user interfaces to select which product references will be integrated, out of all the existing references in the	Medium	U5St_R35

	corporate software (SAP or Finiture)		
U5HR_R1.3	Training		
U5HR_R.1.3.1	The system must be able to model and store the sequence of movements performed by the operator during cobot training	High	U5St_R27
U5HR_R.1.3.3	The system must provide an interface to start and stop a new training sample	Medium	U5St_R29
U5HR_R.1.3.4	The system must provide interfaces to validate the results of the training, providing feedback on the performance of the operation learned (e.g. cycle time, materials used, compared to actual baselines)	Low	U5St_R30
U5HR_R1.4	Operations Control		
U5HR_R.1.4.1	The system must provide user interfaces to confirm the current production order and product information. If the operator does not confirm the robot will not perform any operation.	Medium	U5St_R16, U5St_R19
U5HR_R.1.4.2	The system must alert the operator if there is an error during an operation	Medium	U5St_R19, U5St_R24
U5HR_R.1.4.3	The system must alert the operator when it has finalised an operation step that requires manual intervention	Medium	U5St_R19, U5St_R24

U5HR_R.1.4.4	The cobot(s) must receive instructions from SAP/invoice on the exact containers of the pallet quantity/SKU when packaging and palletizing of custom orders		U5St_R16, U5St_R19
U5HR_R1.5	Performance Monitoring		
U5HR_R.1.5.1	The system must include an interface to allow the user to monitor the state of the network between the different devices	Low	U5St_R23
U5HR_R.1.5.2	The system must provide user interfaces to visualize the evolution of performance KPIs	Low	U5St_R31
U5HR_R.1.5.3	The system must provide user interfaces to monitor performance indicators for the current production order (e.g. mean cycle time, cycle time histogram, paint used, OEE)	Low	U5St_R32
U5HR_R2	Safety		
U5HR_2.1	General		
U5HR_R2.1.1	Must be safe for human	High	U5St_R20, U5St_R36

5.5.4. System level requirements specification for AI enhancing tools

Table 34. System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement Source	Priority	Requirement
U5AI_R1	Scene Perception		
U5AI_R1.1	General		
U5AI_R1.1.1	derived	Medium	Capabilities related to the detection of human poses within a workspace.
U5AI_R1.2	Object Detection		
U5AI_R1.2.1	U5St_R1, U5St_R2	High	Capabilities for detecting multiple printed circuit boards (PCBs) and algorithms that compute the gripping point, which is determined by the

			human-centred teach-in process.
U5AI_R1.2.2	U5St_R8	Medium	Capabilities for suggesting gripping points for a new PCB.
U5AI_R1.2.3	U5St_R5	High	Capabilities for computing an accurate correction transformation for the PCB that is currently being gripped.
U5AI_R1.2.4	U5St_R5	Medium	Virtual Twin of PCB
U5AI_R2	High Level Decision Maker		
U5AI_R2.1	General		
U5AI_R2.1.1	U5St_R9	Medium	Robot behavioural functionalities configuration and execution periods, which including recovery strategies.

5.5.5. System level requirements specification for Social Collaboration

Table 35. System-level requirements specification for software

ID	Requirement Source	Priority	Requirement
U5SC_R1	self-efficacy U5St_R1, U5St_R5, U5St_R7, U5St_R10	high	operators need to be the supervisors of the robotic processes, and be final decision-makers, i.e. need to choose from several PCB handling suggestions
U5SC_R2	physical discomfort U5St_R4, U5St_R8	high	robot process and action planning should eliminate monotonous actions by human to reduce physical strain. The aspects of the task requiring expertise need to remain.
U5SC_R3	time pressure U5St_R9, U5St_R10, U5St_R13	medium	robot needs to indicate to the user where potential errors occurred. human must remain final decision maker deciding if the error/fault/defect is critical or within the tolerance limits

ANNEX B: References

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ANNEX C: Font and colours used in this document

- **Font**

Arial

Open Sans: <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Open+Sans>

- **Colours**

Dark blue: #01547E

Light blue: #4CEE2

Light blue: #DEEBF1

Grey: #606060

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